

Faculty V

Institute of Fluid Dynamics
and Technical Acoustics

A New Approach to Reaction Path Analysis - Application and Evaluation of the SMART Algorithm

Master Thesis
submitted by
Hannah Schweichler

First Advisor: Prof. Dr. Myles. D. Bohon

Second Advisor: Niclas Hanraths, M.Sc.

Technical University Berlin, Faculty V – Institute of Fluid Dynamics and
Technical Acoustics
Berlin, 10. Juni 2020

Affidavit

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbständig und eigenhändig sowie ohne unerlaubte fremde Hilfe und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe.

Ort, Datum

Hannah Schweichler

Zusammenfassung

Diese Thesis untersucht einen neuen Ansatz zur Reaktionpfadanalyse mit Schwerpunkt auf der Stickoxidbildung. Stickoxide sind eine Gefahr für die Umwelt und Gesundheit, deshalb ist die Reduzierung von Emissionen ein wichtiges Anliegen. Das Stickoxid NO wird über verschiedene Reaktionspfade im Reaktionsmechanismus erzeugt. Aufgrund der starken Wechselwirkungen und Interaktionen zwischen den Pfaden, ist es nach wie vor eine Herausforderung die einzelnen Beiträge der Pfade an der Stickoxiderzeugung über die gesamte Flame zu bestimmen.

Eine neue Methode ist der Sub-mechanism Accounting and Reaction Tracing (SMART) Algorithmus. Beginnend mit der Initiierung der Reaktionskette, verfolgt der Algorithmus die Molenströme und ordnet sie den unterschiedlichen Reaktionspfaden zu. Für jede relevante Spezies wird an allen Positionen in der Flame untersucht von welchen Reaktionspfaden sie erzeugt wurde. Anschließend werden die Molenströme, die die Spezies zerlegen, gebührend der Anteile an der Erzeugung den unterschiedlichen Pfaden zugeordnet.

Für die Untersuchung und Bewertung wird der neue Ansatz für die Reaktionpfadanalyse auf verschiedene vorgemischte Methanflammen angewandt und mit einer bestehenden Methode aus der Literatur verglichen. Der Vergleich ergibt, dass bisherige Schwierigkeiten durch den SMART Algorithmus umgangen werden können. Die ermittelten Reaktionspfade zeigen einen stabilen und plausiblen Verlauf über die gesamte Flame und die Qualität der Ergebnisse zeigt sich als unabhängig von dem Äquivalenzverhältnis und dem verwendeten Reaktionsmechanismus.

Abstract

This work investigates a new approach to reaction path analyses with a focus on the NO formation. NO belongs to the nitrogen oxides, which are hazardous pollutants that not only damage the environment but are also a threat to health. Thus, the decrease of emission is a pressing issue.

NO is formed by several pathways in the reaction mechanism. It is challenging, however, to distinguish between the unique contributions of the chemical routes throughout a flame simulation. The reasons are influential interdependencies between the pathways and the increasing complexity of kinetic reaction mechanisms. A new method is the Sub-mechanism Accounting and Reaction Tracing (SMART) algorithm. Starting from the initiations, the approach traces and accounts fluxes to specified pathways. Here each species is analyzed at all flame positions for the pathways leading to its formation. The outgoing fluxes to all possible products are then allocated according to the shares of the distinct routes in the formation.

For the evaluation, the algorithm was applied to a range of premixed methane flames and the results were compared to common analysis from the literature. The investigations revealed that this novel method overcomes the hurdles and limitations of previous methods. The algorithm predicts steady and reasonable results even for minor pathways. The quality of the outcomes is independent of the equivalence ratio and the kinetic mechanism.

Acknowledgements

I would begin by thanking my advisors: A big thank you to Prof. Dr. Myles Bohon, for his excellent supervision and for sharing his knowledge. The time and effort he invested in answering my questions and giving me feedback went above and beyond my expectations. I've learned so much, and I'm very grateful. Also, thank you to Niclas Hanraths for introducing me to everyone and helping me getting started with Python and Cantera. But most of all, thanks to both of them for their kindness and good spirits. I had a pleasant time working on the project and the thesis.

My sincere gratitude goes to Prof. Dr. Achim Schmidt for taking me under his wing and for offering his friendship. The guidance and encouragement I received from him, throughout the years of my studying, cannot be overstated. Thanks to my favorite Irishman, Noel Horan, for the spontaneous getaway when I needed it most and for helping me improve my English over the years. A heartfelt thank you to Venise Gummersbach for all the very productive work sessions. With you, even working through the entire weekend was enjoyable. Thank you for always being there for me.

Finally, to my family for always believing in me and for the unfailing support in my academic education. I couldn't have done it without you.

Contents

Zusammenfassung	V
Abstract	VII
Acknowledgements	IX
List of Symbols	XIII
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 State of current knowledge	2
1.2.1 NO formation	2
1.2.2 Kinetic reaction mechanisms	3
1.2.3 Reaction path analysis	4
1.3 Goal	7
2 Theoretical background	9
2.1 Basic chemical kinetics	9
2.1.1 Elementary reactions	9
2.1.2 Reaction rates and molar fluxes	10
2.2 Formation pathways of nitrogen oxides	12
2.2.1 Thermal mechanism	12
2.2.2 Prompt mechanism	13
2.2.3 NNH mechanism	13
2.2.4 N ₂ O mechanism	14
2.2.5 NO ₂ mechanism	15
2.2.6 HNO mechanism	15
2.2.7 Reburn mechanism	16
3 SMART algorithm	17
3.1 Basic principle	17
3.1.1 Accounting fluxes	18
3.1.2 Flux cases	21
3.1.3 Allocation factors	23
3.1.4 Pools and sources	23

3.2	Execution	25
3.2.1	Pre-processing	26
3.2.2	Pre-calculations	27
3.2.3	Analysis	28
3.2.4	Allocating fluxes	32
3.3	Convergence	34
4	Comparison of reaction path analysis methods	41
4.1	Approach	42
4.2	Results and discussion	48
4.2.1	NO rates of production for the analysed pathways . .	48
4.2.2	Total NO formation	54
4.2.3	Variation of equivalence ratios	57
4.2.4	Reaction mechanism variation	67
5	Conclusions	71
	List of Figures	XV
	List of Tables	XIX
	Bibliography	XXI
	Appendix A	i
	Appendix B	iii

List of Symbols

Latin Symbols

$f_{i,k}$	allocated inflow flux from species i and sub-mechanism k	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
fcf_k	flux correction factor for sub-mechanism k	-
F	total inflow flux	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
F_i	global inflow flux from species i	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$g_{j,k}$	allocated outflow flux to species j in sub-mechanism k	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
G	total outflow flux	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
G_j	global outflow flux to species j	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$h_{j,k}$	initiation flux to species j in sub-mechanism k	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
k	rate coefficient	*
k_b	backward rate coefficient	*
k_f	backward rate coefficient	*
p	pressure	
P	pool	mol m^{-3}
P^n	pool at flame position n	mol m^{-3}
p_k	allocated pool of sub-mechanism k	mol m^{-3}
p_k^n	allocated pool of sub-mechanism k at flame position n	mol m^{-3}
p_k^+	postive allocated pool of sub-mechanism k	mol m^{-3}
r	reaction rate	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
R_∞	universal gas constant	-
s_k	allocated source of sub-mechanism k	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
S	source	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
t_n	time at flame position n	s
T	temperature	K
u_n	velocity at flame position n	m s^{-1}
v	stoichiometric coefficient	-
x_n	spatial position n in flame	m
$X_{NO,k}$	mole fraction for NO produced by sub-mechanism k	-

Greek Symbols

Γ_k	Matrix for allocated fluxes of sub-mechanism k	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$\Gamma_{k,n}$	Matrix for allocated fluxes of sub-mechanism k at flame position n	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$\epsilon_{\Gamma,k,n}^{it}$	residual for allocated fluxes for sub-mechanism k at flame position n and iteration it	-

ϵ_{max}^{it}	maximum residual at iteration it	-
$\epsilon_{\Gamma,n}^{it}$	residual for allocated fluxes at flame position n and iteration it	-
$\epsilon_{H,k}^{it}$	residual for allocation factors for sub-mechanism k and iteration it	-
$\epsilon_{\Lambda,k}^{it}$	residual for allocated pools for sub-mechanism k and iteration it	-
$\epsilon_{\Theta,k}^{it}$	residual for target fluxes for sub-mechanism k and iteration it	-
η_k	allocation factor for sub-mechanism k	-
H_k	Matrix for allocation factors of sub-mechanism k	-
Λ_k	Matrix for allocated pools of sub-mechanism k	mol m^{-3}
Θ_k	Matrix for target fluxes of sub-mechanism k	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$

* units depend on reaction order

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The rising world population combined with increasing technologization and higher standards of living lead to a continuously growing demand for energy. A prognosis from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) shows an increase of almost 50% of the world's energy consumption from the year 2018 until 2050 [1]. Along with the challenges of rising energy demand, the world is facing a climate crisis. The energy sector has been and will be in a state of transition with increasing pressure from the public towards international climate politics. Therefore, the Paris Agreement defines the ultimate goal to prevent a critical change of climate by limiting global warming to well below 2 K [9]. Thus, energy consumption from renewable energy sources gains importance, while those from fossil fuels diminishes proportionally. Nevertheless, energy supply by all sources must rise over the years to meet the growing demand. Consequently, combustion processes will continue to be a significant contributor, not only in the power generation sector but also in transportation, especially in aviation. Evermore stringent requirements towards emission and performance are supposed to diminish the disadvantages of combustion regarding pollution and sustainability. Enhancements of existing combustion methods and research for new concepts are, therefore, pressing issues.

NO is one of the major pollutants in combustion it belongs to the nitrogen oxides (NO_x). NO_x is hazardous not only to the environment but also to health. Acid rain is formed by mixing NO_x and sulfur oxides (SO_x) with rain droplets, causing acidification of lakes and streams as well as damage to trees. Moreover, NO_x is affecting the removal and production of ozone. Considering health issues, elevated NO_x concentrations in the air can lead to respiratory illness and even result in death [43].

In the past, intensive study of NO_x formation allowed various successes to the reduction of NO_x emissions in combustion processes, such as the Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR), the Lean Premixed Combustion (LPC), the Rich Burn – Quick Quench – Lean Burn (RQL), or steam injection [23]. However, as innovation in combustion processes arise, the NO_x formation research must also face new challenges. It is therefore evident that further investigations of NO_x formation are vital for the feasibility of new concepts to meet emission restrictions, ensuring the health of people and prevent environmental damage.

A key factor for success is the profound understanding of the underlying combustion kinetics that help to comprehend the complex dependencies in pollutant formation.

1.2 State of current knowledge

1.2.1 NO formation

NO is one of the major pollutants in combustion. Its formation has been studied for almost a century by many scientists. The most prominent formation pathways comprise the Thermal mechanism, the Prompt mechanism, the fuel mechanism, the NNH mechanism and the N_2O mechanism.

Fig. 1.1: NO formation pathways and their approximate significance in dependence on the conditions [23]

The distinct mechanisms are initiated under different circumstances so that they gain or forfeit importance due to considered combustion applications. The formation depends on many parameters, including combustion temperature, pressure, residence time, and fuel. For instance, Thermal NO is initiated at high temperatures only and is produced slowly in the exhaust downstream from the flame front [44]. Whereas, Prompt NO is produced rapidly in the flame front, profiting from high concentrations of CH-radicals. The fuel mechanism considers the formation of NO due to fuel-bound nitrogen. It is mainly observed in coal combustion [44]. The NNH and the N_2O mechanisms profit from lower temperatures than the Thermal and gain importance in lean conditions. Figure 1.1 gives an overview of the main formation pathways and their significance in combustion applications. A more detailed explanation of NO formation pathways relevant to this work follows in section 2.2, including further formation

routes and mechanisms that concern the reduction of NO, like the Reburn mechanism.

1.2.2 Kinetic reaction mechanisms

Very complex and nonlinear dependencies in NO formation make it impossible to gain full understanding solely by experimental measurements. Therefore, there are several reaction mechanisms to the model kinetic chemistry of combustion. The complexity correlates with the accuracy of predictions and the chemistry of fuel. For instance, a H₂ combustion comprises only 40 elementary reactions for adequate results, while a mechanism for more complex fuels, like hydrocarbons, easily contains a few hundred up to thousands of reactions [23]. The development is an ongoing process, including continuous revisions. The following will briefly describe the mechanisms used in this work.

The GRI-Mech 3.0 [41](GRI) was developed at the University of California at Berkeley, Stanford University, the University of Texas at Austin, and SRI International by several scientists. The research was sponsored by the Gas Research Institute and resulted in a detailed kinetic reaction mechanism for natural gas combustion that contains 325 reactions and 53 species. The model provides reliable chemistry for methane and ethane, while the chemistry for propane consists only of a minor set of kinetics. Additionally, the GRI comprises NO_x formation and reburning chemistry. The primary NO_x formation routes are the Thermal, the Prompt based on HCN initiation, NNH, and N₂O. The GRI is the successor to the GRI-Mech 2.0. Among other enhancements, CH kinetics have been improved, which is particularly interesting for Prompt NO. The GRI seeks to deliver a complete set of elementary reaction steps and uses a global optimization procedure to ensure the fit of rate parameters to a wide range of pressures and temperatures.

A different approach was made by the combustion research group at the University of California at San Diego. The UCSD mechanism [39] (UCSD) consists of the minimum amount of reactions and species to model specific processes so that uncertainties in minor reaction steps don't compromise the results of the overall process. The UCSD model focuses on conditions relevant to flames, high-temperature ignition, and detonations. The main mechanism covers chemistry for C₁-C₃ alkanes and C₁-C₂ alcohols. A sub-mechanism for nitrogen chemistry is also available, including the Thermal pathway, HCN-initiated Prompt pathway, as well as N₂O, and NNH routes.

The GDF-Kin 3.0_NCN (GDF) is the latest update of previous GDF-Kin mechanisms by El Bakali et al. [13]. GDF-Kin 2.0 is a detailed kinetic mechanism specifically designed for natural gas oxidation in very large conditions. The model comprises chemistry for major and minor C₁-C₆ alkanes in natural gas. The mechanism was expanded by adding the NO_x chemistry from Dagaut et

al.[2] to the existing hydrocarbon chemistry and was then released as GDF-Kin 3.0. The NO_x sub-mechanism models NO produced by all prominent pathways (Thermal, Prompt, NNH, N₂O), as well as reburn chemistry. The NO formation for Prompt NO was altered due to the discovery of a new initiation pathway by Moskaleva and Lin [32]. Thus, the GDF-Kin 3.0_NCN mechanism also covers the NCN-initiated Prompt route, whereas the GRI and the UCSD describe HCN-initiated Prompt NO. Ultimately, the full model contains 883 reversible reactions and 121 species.

Another mechanism also including the NCN-initiated pathway for Prompt NO is the Konnov0.6 [26]. The NCN route was added by Konnov to the existing release Konnov0.5, which is a detailed reaction mechanism for modeling combustions of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, C₁-C₂ alcohols and C₁-C₃ alkanes. H/C/N/O reactions for in-flame NO_x formation and reburning chemistry exist as well. The current version (Release 0.6) contains 129 species and 1231 reactions.

1.2.3 Reaction path analysis

For every simulation, post-processing is a crucial step to extract valuable information from the generated data. The interpretation of results relies on the ability to make interactions and dependencies in the data accessible and to illustrate them in a comprehensible manner. A common approach is the reaction path analysis (RPA), respectively reaction path diagrams. This method calculates for each reaction, the percentage of contribution to the formation (or depletion) of every species. A local analysis determines the reaction paths for a single location in a steady or for a specific time in a time-dependent problem; whereas, the integral method considers the whole combustion process. Reaction path diagrams illustrate the results as a directed graph. Figure 2.1 in section 2.2 shows an example for a reaction path diagram of the Prompt mechanism. Reaction path analysis is an efficient tool to outline the overall routes and to emphasize their importance in the formation of a species. Anyhow, it remains difficult to distinguish between the distinct sub-mechanisms of NO formation throughout the whole flame. The distinct chemical routes often spatially overlap within the flame and certain intermediate species contribute to multiple formation mechanisms. Considering NO formation, previous research reveal several approaches to extract the contribution of the different pathways, like Thermal, or Prompt [8, 17, 19, 18, 24, 34, 45, 37, 36]. Table 4.1 yields an overview of selected methods. A common approach is to simulate the flame with varying sets of nitrogen chemistry. For example, for the calculation of the contribution of the Thermal mechanism, a simulation with the whole set of nitrogen chemistry is carried out and, additionally, a simulation without the initiation reactions from thermal NO is conducted. Afterwards, the results

of the total NO rate of production (ROP) of the incomplete set of nitrogen chemistry is subtracted from the results of the simulation with the complete set. Accordingly, the difference in the ROP is allocated to the Thermal mechanism. However, the repeated simulations of the flame are time-consuming and the removal of reactions might have unforeseen side effects if, e.g., the concentrations of intermediate species are affected.

Bohon et al. [4, 5, 6] presented a new approach to reaction path analysis that conquers these limitations. The authors propose a method that traces an element through the network of reactions from an initiation element to a target element and allocates fluxes between all intermediate elements to defined sub-mechanisms. For NO_x formation, the nitrogen is traced from the initiation element N₂ to the target species NO. For each position in the flame, the total molar fluxes between the nitrogen-containing intermediate species (e.g., HCN, NH) are calculated and then allocated to the distinct routes of NO formation. Figure 1.2 shows an example of a reaction path analysis using this method. The individual contributions from the distinct sub-mechanisms

Fig. 1.2: Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric propane flame using the element tracing method proposed by Bohon et al. [4]

are represented by the colored lines. The sum (total) of all contributions is shown by the black dashed line, while the total rate of production (ROP) is represented by the black circle markers. The results illustrate the share of the total NO formation from each sub-mechanism throughout the flame. However, the total does not match the ROP of NO at all flame positions. Consequently, there are still problems, though the overall concept achieves reasonable results. Furthermore, the approach requires a Burnout sub-mechanism, which captures the NO formation from species that accumulate in the flame. Ideally, these

rates should be distributed among the existing sub-mechanisms, depending on their contribution to the accumulation. Moreover, the application of the post-processing tool is restricted to a single chemical kinetic reaction mechanism, which limits its applicability. Coulmann [11] developed in his work an algorithm that implements the element tracing method and that overcomes the existing deficiencies. The concept of pool terms was introduced to capture the accumulation of every species in every flame position. The NO formation from an accumulated species is now accurately allocated to the sub-mechanisms, depending on their participation in the accumulation. Figure 1.3 exhibits an example of the enhanced RPA. Again, the various colored lines represent the contributions of the sub-mechanisms. The red dashed line is the sum of the distinct contributions, expressing the total NO formation, and the black circle markers show the ROP of NO.

The results reveal an improved agreement of the NO ROP and the summed

Fig. 1.3: Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric propane flame using the algorithm developed by Coulmann. [11]

total NO formation calculated by the algorithms. Moreover, it confirms that the Burnout mechanism has become obsolete and is no longer required to capture the total formation. Besides, the kinetic reaction mechanism is now a user's input to the algorithm, so that the range of applications is broadened. The updated algorithm is named Sub-Mechanism Accounting and Reaction Tracing (SMART) algorithm.

1.3 Goal

The ultimate objective of this thesis is to show the applicability of the post-processing algorithm SMART and to emphasize the benefits of this new approach to reaction path analysis (RPA).

On that account, the algorithm is applied to a range of canonical flames focusing on variations in equivalent ratios and reaction mechanisms. First, the work examines the convergence behavior for the applications since reliable and rapid convergence is crucial to the practicalness. In the next step, the results from the SMART algorithm are compared to those from a reaction path analysis as proposed in the literature.

As mentioned above the algorithm was developed to compare the NO formation contribution of defined sub-mechanisms to deflagration and combustion problems. Anyhow, this work is limited to premixed stationary flames to gain a more fundamental insight into the advantages and limitations of the analysed RPA methods.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Basic chemical kinetics

The analysis of reaction paths is based on the science of chemical kinetics. Therefore, this section provides an overview of basic knowledge.

Chemical kinetics engage in the actual physical processes, while the more universally known thermodynamic laws engage in the determination of "ideal" end states of reaction processes. The advantage of chemical kinetics is that this science provides information on how fast reactions proceed and on whether or more precisely under which conditions an equilibrium state can be achieved. Therefore, the focus is not on the more prominent macroscopic global reactions that represent overall processes in which reactants are converted to anticipated products but on the underlying microscopic elementary reactions.

2.1.1 Elementary reactions

An *elementary reaction* takes place on a molecular level exactly as it is described by its reaction equation [22]. This sets the key feature of physical collisions between particles (atoms, molecules, radicals). Another characteristic is that the reactions are always reversible.

An example that easily emphasizes the difference between global and elementary reactions is the formation of water:

For the global reaction 2.1, two H₂ molecules have to simultaneously collide with O₂ and react in a way that two water molecules are produced, which is statistically a very unlikely event. The reaction 2.2, on the other hand, is probable, since molecules, like H₂, usually have a high concentration and radicals, like OH, are highly reactive.

When OH and H₂ collide atomic hydrogen is abstracted from the molecular H₂ by the OH radicals to produce water and an H radical. 2.2 is one of the many elementary reactions that are required for the overall process described by 2.1. For example Baulch et al. declare 38 necessary elementary reactions

for this comparatively simple process [3]. More complex phenomena demand a much higher amount. Despite the large variety, all elementary reactions can be categorized by molecularity into three types: unimolecular, bimolecular and trimolecular. Due to the required collision, higher molecularity is statistically very unlikely and therefore irrelevant. An *unimolecular* reaction involves only one reactant and includes bond breaking reactions and isomerization reactions:

Hence, it defines the rearrangement or dissociation of a molecule. Despite the uni-molecularity, a collision partner, like an inert particle, is still essential. Therefore, the reaction equation is often stated as:

A *bimolecular* reaction requires two reactants and occurs most frequently. The reaction is either an addition or an abstraction. In addition reactions, radicals and molecules merge while in abstraction reactions the radical divest the molecule of an atom (2.2). The reactions are described by the equations

or

Trimolecular reactions are usually recombinations. The third body of the reaction is most commonly only collision partner. The procedure is according to the equations

or

or

2.1.2 Reaction rates and molar fluxes

The reaction rate expresses the formation or consumption of a species. It is defined as the rate of change for the concentration of a species per time unit $[\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{ s}}]$ and is standardized with the stoichiometric coefficient. For the arbitrary reaction equation 2.10 the reaction rate is defined by 2.11.

$$r = \frac{1}{v_A} \frac{d[A]}{dt} = \frac{1}{v_B} \frac{d[B]}{dt} = \frac{1}{v_C} \frac{d[C]}{dt} = \frac{1}{v_D} \frac{d[D]}{dt} \quad (2.11)$$

Here A, B, \dots are species involved. The stoichiometric coefficients v_A, v_B, \dots have negative algebraic signs for educts and positive signs for products, whereas, in reaction equations absolute values are used. The brackets $[]$ symbolize concentrations of species. The rate r is empirically described by rate laws. For the consumption of A the reaction rate is expressed according to

$$r = \frac{1}{v_A} \frac{d[A]}{dt} = k[A]^a[B]^b \quad (2.12)$$

with k as the rate coefficient. The rate coefficient is non-linear temperature-dependent and empirically described by the *Arrhenius equation*. The exponents a and b are reaction orders. For global reactions they depend on experimental conditions so that the determination is nontrivial. As for elementary reactions the reaction orders are equal to the stoichiometric coefficient, so that they can easily be measured and simplify equation 2.11 to

$$r = \frac{1}{v_A} \frac{d[A]}{dt} = k[A]^{|v_A|}[B]^{|v_B|}. \quad (2.13)$$

The order for the overall reaction is defined by the sum of the respective reaction orders (in this case: $a + b$). Therefore, elementary reactions have reaction orders from 1 to 3. An unimolecular reaction is a first-order reaction. Consequently, the rate belonging to the reaction equation 2.3 is directly proportional to the molar concentration of the species $[A]$ and is calculated according to

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -k[A] \quad \text{with } v_A = -1. \quad (2.14)$$

Following this, bimolecular reactions are second-order and trimolecular reaction principally obey a third-order rate law.

As mentioned earlier, elementary reactions are always reversible so that the arbitrary reaction 2.10 adjusts to

with subscripts f and b for the forward and backward rate coefficients. The corresponding rates are defined by

$$r_f = k_f[A]^{|v_A|}[B]^{|v_B|} \quad (2.16)$$

and

$$r_b = k_b[C]^{|v_C|}[D]^{|v_D|}. \quad (2.17)$$

The difference between 2.16 and 2.17 is the net rate of the reaction. It goes zero, when a reaction reaches equilibrium (eq) and the forward and backward reaction proceed at finite and equal rates. Otherwise a species is either produced or consumed.

$$r_f - r_b = k_f[A]_{eq}^{v_A}[B]_{eq}^{v_B} - k_b[C]_{eq}^{v_C}[D]_{eq}^{v_D} = 0 \quad (2.18)$$

Net rates are essential for reaction paths analyses, since they determine the molar fluxes. A molar flux is defined as the change of concentration of a species. Hence, it is the product of the corresponding reaction rate and stoichiometric coefficient. The reaction path analyses are conducted for complex reaction mechanisms, which comprise numerous elementary reactions; therefore, molar fluxes are calculated for species over a set of reactions. Considering a reaction mechanism is composed of S species and R reactions, all elementary reactions are generally defined according to

Here e and p refer to educts and products. Following this, the change of concentration, or respectively the molar flux, of the considered species i in the elementary reaction r is sum over formation (>0) and the depletion (<0).

$$\frac{d[A_{ri}]}{dt} = v_{ri}^{(e)} k_r^f \prod_{s=1}^S [A_s]^{v_{rs}^{(e)}} + v_{ri}^{(p)} k_r^b \prod_{s=1}^S [A_s]^{v_{rs}^{(p)}}, \quad (2.20)$$

To calculate the molar flux of species i for the mechanism all fluxes are simply summed over the set of reactions according to

$$\frac{d[A_i]}{dt} = \sum_{r=1}^R \frac{d[A_{ri}]}{dt}. \quad (2.21)$$

2.2 Formation pathways of nitrogen oxides

2.2.1 Thermal mechanism

The chain of reactions corresponding to the Thermal mechanism was postulated by Zeldovich in 1946 [46].

The formation of NO via this route is limited to the first reaction 2.22. The high activation energy of the nitrogen triple bond causes a low reaction rate, which is only sufficiently increased at high temperatures. Hence, this mechanism is considered most relevant at elevated temperatures, resulting in the naming 'Thermal'. The molecular nitrogen produced in the initiation reaction 2.22 is then depleted by the reactions 2.23 and 2.24 to form more NO.

2.2.2 Prompt mechanism

The Prompt mechanism is initiated by the reaction of N_2 with CH_n radicals, including C, CH, CH_2 among others. CH radicals are formed as intermediates in the flame front. Thus, Prompt NO formation is mainly observed in the reaction zone under rich conditions [44]. The mechanism was first discovered by Fenimore [15]. The name 'Prompt' was added due to its rapid production rate of NO in comparison to the slow Thermal route. Fenimore [15] established that the mechanism is initiated by hydrocarbon radicals and nitrogen molecules reacting to hydrocyanic acid and nitrogen atoms.

For 30 years the reaction 2.25 has been considered the most important initiation reaction compared to less the relevant initiation steps 2.26 to 2.28 [21].

In the year 2000 Moskaleva and Lin [32] presented a new and spin conservative pathway, proposing NCN and N as products of the reaction between CH and N_2 .

After the initiation of the prompt mechanism NO is rapidly formed via a reaction chain including multiple nitrogen fixing intermediate species, like NCN, HCN, CN, NH and N. Figure 2.1 shows a scheme of Prompt NO in the reaction zone. This reaction path is initiated by reaction 2.29.

2.2.3 NNH mechanism

The significance of the NNH radical in nitrogen chemistry was first proposed by Miller et al. [31], who considered NNH as an intermediate in the formation of

Fig. 2.1: Scheme of prompt-NO in the flame front of a rich $\text{CH}_4\text{-O}_2\text{-N}_2$ flame based on rate of production analysis at the NCN peak location with the GDFkin@3.0 NCN mechanism [29]

N_2 from NO. Hence, it was first established as a key species in a NO reduction pathway produced by the reaction of NO with NH_2 .

In the year 1995 Dean and Bozzelli [7] suggested NNH as possible new route for the formation of NO. The introduced NNH mechanism consists of the following sequence of reaction [7]:

The reaction 2.30 initiates the process while NO is formed via reaction 2.31. NH as a product of 2.31 reacts under lean conditions further with O_x and produces an additional NO. However, a study of Klippenstein et al. [25] indicates that $\text{NO} + \text{NH}$ is only a minor channel for $\text{NNH} + \text{O}$, leading to less significant contributions to the overall formation of NO compared to other mechanisms. Earlier estimations from theoretical works suggest a more important role for the NNH chemistry [27, 28]. The actual importance of the NNH channel to the formation of NO remains a controversial discussed topic of research [16].

2.2.4 N_2O mechanism

The nitrous oxide mechanism is most significant in lean flames and at low temperatures. Lean conditions oppress the production of hydrocarbon radicals so that Prompt NO is less relevant. Besides, temperatures below the significant temperature of Thermal NO (ca. 1800 K) promote the formation of NO via the N_2O mechanism further, since (similar to the Thermal mechanism) its initiation requires O-atoms (2.32) [30].

Due to the three-body-reaction in 2.32, N_2O formation is enhanced at elevated pressures, making the nitrous oxide route a prior contributor of NO formation in lean premixed combustion in gas turbine engines [10].

Once the mechanism has been initiated, NO is mainly produced via the following sequence of reactions [47]:

2.2.5 NO_2 mechanism

NO_2 is the second major component of nitrogen oxides next to NO. It is initially formed via the recombination of NO and O [47],

2.37 - 2.39 are further reactions leading to the consumption or depletion of NO_2 [47].

2.2.6 HNO mechanism

HNO (nitrosyl hydride, azanone, nitroxyl) is a key species in the formation of NOx. The species reacts with other intermediates, like O, OH, and H to form NO. But it is also linked to NO reduction depending on the combustion conditions. A significant depletion of NO is, for example, attributed to the reaction 2.40 under oxy-fuel conditions [14]. Reactions 2.41-2.43 also contribute to the formation, respectively consumption of NO via the HNO scheme [47]. HNO reactions are experimentally still poorly investigated, especially in high temperature regions. Thus, the modeling of its kinetic chemistry continues to be problematic [14].

2.2.7 Reburn mechanism

The reburn mechanism focuses on NO removal reactions. It was, therefore, early investigated and is used as a NO_x reduction strategy in practical systems [31]. NO is recycled by reacting with species from the C₁ radical pool to form HCN (or CN) [33]. The hydrogen cyanide is then either converted to N₂ or back to NO, depending on the radicals present. Accordingly, this mechanism can be utilized in form of staged combustion to reduce NO. In the first stage the fuel is oxidated under lean up to stoichiometric conditions. Then the secondary stage takes places: In the reburning zone natural gas is injected to activate the reburn route. The combustion is completed in the third staged by air injection [12].

C, CH, CH₂, CH₃ and HCCO have been identified as initiating species by researchers in several studies [42, 31, 38, 20, 12]. Again, the relevance of the distinct initiation reactions relies on the conditions triggered by the combustion process. The ketyl-radical HCCO, for instance, is most important under various conditions [12], including very fuel-rich combustions [38]. The following sequence of reactions shows significant initiation reactions:

The HCNO formed in reaction 2.50 is then either converted to HCN by reacting with H radicals or converted back to NO by reacting with O or OH radicals.

3 SMART algorithm

The SMART algorithm is a post-processing tool for conducting reaction path analyses. It is coded using the programming language *Python 3.7*. Chemical kinetic calculations are performed with the help of the open-source software *Cantera*. In the following sections, the basic principle of the analysis is explained, and the execution via the developed algorithm is abstracted and simplified as a flow chart (*Nassi-Shneidermann-chart* [35]). A special focus is on the newly applied convergence criteria of the algorithm.

3.1 Basic principle

In this section, the basic principle of the new approach to reaction path analysis is explained. The purpose of the SMART algorithm is to provide an improved reaction path analysis. A specified reaction path (sub-mechanism) for the formation of a species starts with one or more initiation reactions where the tracing element is unfixed from the initiation species and 'traced' through the following reactions. The products of the first reactions are intermediate species, which then (repeatedly) react to form other intermediate species and, ultimately, the target species. For example, in a reaction path analysis for NO formation, the initiation species is N_2 , and the tracing element is N. The intermediate species are all species that contain the tracing element. The net rates of the reactions determine the molar fluxes between the linked species, as described in section 2.1.2. The difficulty of the analysis is that distinct pathways overlap and reactions are not attributable to a single sub-mechanism. The only exceptions are the initiation reactions, which are singular to the initiated reaction path. Figure 3.1 shows an arbitrary, simplified example for a formation pathway, starting from an initiation species via the intermediate species A-H through to the target species.

The red fluxes emerging from the initiation species are the initiation fluxes, and the sum of the green fluxes leading to the target species is the target flux. Reaction pathways, like the one in figure 3.1, change for every position in the flame since they depend on chemical kinetics, respectively on the state of the gas. Consequently, a full reaction path analysis requires the examination of the formation and depletion of all relevant species for every position in the flame. In every step of the procedure, molar fluxes due to shared reactions have to be accounted for the sub-mechanisms.

Fig. 3.1: Demonstration of a reaction path

3.1.1 Accounting fluxes

This subsection presents the different kinds of fluxes, their relationships, and the rules of accounting for the reaction path analysis. All provided demonstrations show the formation and depletion of a single species A for a single position in the flame. As mentioned before, the actual analysis is conducted for all relevant species and flame positions. The execution is presented in the corresponding subsection 3.2.

Fig. 3.2: Demonstration of total fluxes

Figure 3.2 demonstrates the total molar fluxes into and out of species A. By convention, all fluxes into the species have a positive sign while the fluxes out of the species have a negative sign. The flux F is the total inflow to species A and represents the total formation of the species. The flux G , on the other hand, is the total outflow of the species A and, therefore, represent its depletion. If F and G are equal the species is neither produced nor consumed. In most cases, however, the concentration of species A is either increasing ($F > G$) or decreasing ($F < G$). The difference between the total inflow and the total outflow is the total net flux, also called the source S . The Pool P represents the accumulation of the species A in the flame, due to the source and is further discussed in subsections 3.1.2 and 3.1.4. The direction and quantity of the source depend on F and G .

$$F - G = S \quad (3.1)$$

The total inflow to species A is due to several reactants B_i producing the A, while the outflow is caused by species A being depleted to form several products C_j . The fluxes between the reactants and A are the global inflow fluxes F_i and the fluxes between A and the products are G_j . Thus, the total fluxes are the sums of the respective global fluxes,

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^I F_i \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$G = \sum_j^J G_j. \quad (3.3)$$

Global fluxes describe the fluxes between species as they are defined by the chemical reactions (2.16 - 2.18). The reaction path analysis allocates shares of the fluxes to sub-mechanisms, the so-called allocated fluxes $f_{i,k}$ or $g_{j,k}$, depending on the direction. The subscripts i , j , and k correspond to the respective reactants, products, and sub-mechanisms. The sum of allocated fluxes over all sub-mechanisms for a reactant or product equals the corresponding global flux,

$$F_i = \sum_k f_{i,k} \quad (3.4)$$

and

$$G_j = \sum_k g_{j,k}. \quad (3.5)$$

The same applies for the source S and the allocated sources s_k .

$$S = \sum_{k=1}^K s_k, \quad (3.6)$$

Fig. 3.3: Demonstration of accounting fluxes

The accounting of fluxes by the reaction path analysis is demonstrated in figure 3.3. The allocation of the global outflow fluxes depends on a sub-mechanism's contribution to the formation of the species. The unique contribution is expressed by the ratio of the sub-mechanism's inflow to the total inflow and is called the allocation factor η_k . In general, the outflow fluxes are allocated according to

$$g_{j,k} = \eta_k G_j \quad \text{with } 0 \leq \eta_k \leq 1. \quad (3.7)$$

An exception is made, when shares of the outflow flux G_j are initiation fluxes $h_{j,k}$. As stated before, initiation fluxes are singular to a sub-mechanism and, therefore, they must not be allocated. This leads to the introduction of the term G'_j , which is the share of the global flux G_j that has to be allocated to the distinct pathways. Consequently, it is the difference between the G'_j and the sum of the initiation fluxes $h_{j,k}$.

$$G'_j = G_j - \sum_k h_{j,k} \quad (3.8)$$

The limitation leads to two different accounting cases.

- I $G'_j > 0$: Here the direction of the flux is preserved so that the allocation proceeds according to the routine of 3.7: $g'_{j,k} = \eta_k G'_j$.
- II $G'_j < 0$: For the second case, the direction of the flux changes. Consequently, the flux is an outflow from C_j and must be allocated according to the flux balance and allocation factor of the species C_j . The general equation is the same as for case i, except for the adjusted allocation factor.

Both cases bear the term $g'_{j,k}$ for their respective species. To finalize the accounting the initiation flux of the analyzed sub-mechanism must be added to the allocated flux $g'_{j,k}$

$$g_{j,k} = g'_{j,k} + h_{j,k}. \quad (3.9)$$

The last step might alter the direction of the flux again so that the attribution to the species must be re-adjusted accordingly.

If a species is only formed by one sub-mechanism k , $\eta_k = 1$, and the allocated outflow fluxes of this species equal the global outflow fluxes. If more than one sub-mechanism is involved in the formation of the species, the allocation factors have to be determined by the unique contributions. The equations for the allocation factors depend on different flux cases since the sources change directions due to the total fluxes and must either be issued as additional inflow or outflow flux. Further explanations of the flux cases and allocation factors follow in the next sections.

3.1.2 Flux cases

Four different flux cases determine the calculation of allocation factors and sources. Figure 3.4 illustrates characteristics for each case. The four cases depend on the total net flux, respectively the direction of the source, and the state of the pool. As defined earlier, the pool represents the accumulation of the species in the flame. Therefore, it is similar to the concentration of a species. But unlike concentrations, the pool can go below zero. The possibility of a negative accumulation is introduced to acknowledge diffusion processes in the flame. The flux cases are defined as followed:

- I The species A is formed at a greater rate than it is depleted. Hence, the inflow flux is greater than the outflow flux, so that the source is an additional outflow and leads to a further population of the already positive pool.

Fig. 3.4: Flux cases

- II** The total net flux is here also positive so that the source is negative and populates the pool. However, in this case, the pool has been drawn from before at a greater rate than it was populated so that the accumulation is yet negative.
- III** The species is depleted at a greater rate than it is formed. Therefore, the total net flux is negative. Consequently, the source is an additional inflow flux. The pool for the species has already accumulated earlier in the flame and is, therefore, positive.
- IV** The total net flux is here negative as well, but as opposed to the third case, the pool is already negative. This means that diffusion transports

the species forward from a later accumulation in the flame with the result that the species is now depleted to form other species.

3.1.3 Allocation factors

The SMART algorithm converts global fluxes into allocated fluxes for each sub-mechanism with the help of allocation factors (3.5). An allocation factor is the ratio of inflow fluxes from a particular sub-mechanism to the total inflow into a species; therefore, its specification depends on the flux cases. For the general definition of the allocation factors only the total net fluxes are relevant so that cases I and II lead to the same equation and the cases III and IV provide a further equation.

For the cases, I and II the net flux is positive so that the source is an additional output. Hence, only the fluxes from the reactants ($F, f_{i,k}$) flow into the species and must, therefore, be considered for the allocation.

$$\eta_{I/II,k} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,k}}{F} \quad (\text{Flux Cases I and II}) \quad (3.10)$$

For the cases, III and IV on the contrary, the total net fluxes are negative. Consequently, the source is directed towards the species and is, therefore, issued as an inflow flux. The allocation factor is now the ratio of the allocated inflow fluxes ($f_{i,k}$) plus the allocated source (s_k) to the total inflow flux (F) plus the total source (S).

$$\eta_{III/IV,k} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,k} + s_k}{F + S} \quad (\text{Flux Cases III and IV}) \quad (3.11)$$

Though the general formula of the allocation factor for the cases III and IV is the same 3.11, there is a further distinction regarding the allocated sources (s_k). The rules for the calculation of the sources are given in the following section.

3.1.4 Pools and sources

The pool represents the accumulation for a species and it is one of the criteria for the declaration of the current flux case. Therefore, the pool is ultimately required to allocate the molar fluxes and sources. The state of the pool for a species is changed throughout the flame by the source. A positive source is an inflow for the pool and, therefore, contributes to the population, while a negative flux is an outflow and draws from the pool. If the species depletion of a species equals the formation, the source goes zero and the pool remains unchanged. Note that the signs of the source are opposite compared to the balance for the species since now the system boundaries belong to the balance

of the pool. The current state of a species' pool is calculated by adding the contribution from the source for every time step in the flame to the existing pool.

$$P^n = P^{n-1} + S_n dt \quad (3.12)$$

For a spatially resolved flame simulation, the time step is obtained from the positions (x) and the corresponding the velocities (u) according to

$$dt = t_n - t_{n-1} \quad (3.13)$$

with

$$t_n = t_{n-1} + \frac{2(x_n - x_{n-1})}{u_n - u_{n-1}} \quad (3.14)$$

The pool of a species can also be divided among the sub-mechanisms according to their contributions to the accumulation. Here the contribution of sub-mechanism's pool (p_k) is calculated with the corresponding allocated source (s_k)

$$p_k^n = p_k^{n-1} + s_{k,n} dt. \quad (3.15)$$

The allocated sources (s_k) being responsible for the population of the pool are described by the flux cases I and II. Since these sources are issued as an extra outflow of the species, their allocation is equally treated as the allocation of global outflow fluxes (G_j). Furthermore, the same allocation factor ($\eta_{I/II,k}$) as in 3.10 applies because of the considered flux cases.

$$s_k = \eta_{I/II,k} S \quad (\text{Flux Cases I and II}) \quad (3.16)$$

The unique contributions of the sub-mechanisms to the pool are important when in flux case III the allocated sources are issued as additional inflow fluxes and needed for the calculation of the allocation factor ($\eta_{III/IV,k}$) (3.11). For the third case, the pool is positive. Hence, the species has already been accumulated in the flame. The source that draws from the pool is allocated with the help of the ratio of the accumulated contributions to the pool by the sub-mechanisms (p_k) to the total pool of the species (P). Albeit, the overall pool P is positive in this flux case, one or more allocated pools p_k can still be negative due to the unique contributions at former flame positions. But a sub-mechanism can only draw from its pool p_k , if it is positive.

$$s_k = \frac{p_k^+}{\sum_k p_k^+} S \quad (\text{Flux Case III}) \quad (3.17)$$

Here the superscript + indicates a positive accumulation. For all sub-mechanism with a negative pool the source is zero ($s_k = 0$).

In the fourth flux case, the source expresses diffusion in the flame. For this

scenario, the flux correction factor fcf_k is introduced. The flux correction factor of a species is a sub-mechanism's overall contribution to its formation divided by the overall formation by all sub-mechanisms. The allocation of the source proceeds according to

$$s_k = fcf_k S \quad (\text{Flux Case IV}) \quad (3.18)$$

with

$$fcf_k = \frac{\int_{t=0}^{t_{end}} \sum_i f_{i,k} dt}{\int_{t=0}^{t_{end}} F dt}. \quad (3.19)$$

3.2 Execution

This section describes the execution of the reaction path analysis for a spatially resolved simulation with the help of a flow chart. For reasons of clarity and comprehensibility the overall flow chart is divided into multiple sections:

- **pre-processing:** Reading and editing of input data
- **pre-calculations:** Calculating net, global and initiation fluxes, as well as pools
- **analysis:** Allocating fluxes and pools; determining target fluxes

Besides, the function for the allocation of the fluxes is extracted from the whole algorithm to show the iterative procedure in detail.

Since the algorithm is coded using the dynamically-typed programming language *Python*, there are no explicit declarations for the variables necessary. Anyhow, a declaration header for the flow chart with all variables and their corresponding data types plus short descriptions is given in the appendix B. The names of the variables are, however, in most cases self-explanatory.

The algorithm calculates several different fluxes between intermediate species (global fluxes, initiation fluxes, and allocated fluxes). Each type of these fluxes is stored in a corresponding matrix, where the first two dimensions represent the intermediate species. Following this, every row i (first dimension = 1.D) and every column j (2.D) represents an intermediate species. By convention, the direction of flux is from species j to species i . If species j is depleted by species i , the flux is stored at a matrix position (i, j) and if species j is formed by species i , the flux is stored at position (j, i) . This way all inflow fluxes ($F_i, f_{i,k}$) for a species are stored in its row and all outflow fluxes ($G_j, g_{j,k}$) are saved in its column. For the allocated fluxes ($f_{i,k}, g_{j,k}$) an additional dimension is needed for the k sub-mechanisms. Since the position in the matrix determines the directions of the fluxes, only absolute values are saved.

3.2.1 Pre-processing

In the pre-processing part of the program, the algorithm loads the input files, stores the data on variables, and adds further needed information. The procedure is described by functions and assignments in the flow chart 3.5.

<pre> flame_sim,setup,sub_mechs,react_mech ← InputGUI() # Loads input files via user interface: 1. Flame simulation file 2. Setup file 3. Sub-mechanism file 4. Reaction mechanism file </pre>	
<pre> flame_dict ← ReadFlame(flame_sim) # Reads flame simulation file and combines data in a dictionary </pre>	
<pre> t ← CalcTime(flame_dict) # Calculates time vector for flame simulation </pre>	
<pre> flame_dict ← t Add time vector to dictionary </pre>	
<pre> inputs_dict ← CreateDict(setup,sub_mechs) # Loads and combines input data from setup file and sub-mechanism file in a dictionary </pre>	
<pre> gas ← cantera.Solution(react_mech) # Sets reaction mechanism for Cantera </pre>	
<pre> ini_reacs_list ← FindIniReactions(inputs_dict,gas) # Finds all reactions containing the Initiation Reactant and stores them in a list </pre>	
<pre> inputs_dict ← ini_reacs_list # Add list of reactions to dictionary </pre>	
<pre> undef_sub_reacs ← UndefSubMech(inputs_dict,gas) # Assigns all yet unassigned initiation reactions to the undefined sub-mechanism </pre>	
<pre> int_species ← FindIntSpecies(Tracking_Element,gas) # Finds all species containing the tracking element and lists them as intermediate species </pre>	
<pre> inputs_dict ← int_species # Add list of intermediate species to dictionary </pre>	
<pre> reactions_between_species,int_reactions ← FindIntReactions(inputs_dict,gas) # Finds all reactions between the intermediate species and stores them once in nested lists with affiliation to the intermediate species and then in a simple list as a series of items </pre>	

Fig. 3.5: Flow chart for the pre-processing of the SMART algorithm

The first function loads an input GUI so that the user can choose the input files for the reaction path analysis from the directories. There are four necessary inputs for conducting the analysis:

1. **flame simulation file:** Includes the data from the simulation (temperature, pressure, position, velocity and molar fractions for each species)

2. **setup file:** Includes setup information for the reaction path analysis (initiation species, tracing element, target species, RPA tolerance, threshold)
3. **sub-mechanism file:** Includes the names of the sub-mechanisms for the analysis plus the numbers of the initiation reactions from the reaction mechanism. The directions of initiation species must be defined too. Therefore they're stored in nested lists, where the first list holds forward reactions, the second list holds backward reactions and for the third list both directions are initiating the sub-mechanism. For the Thermal sub-mechanism in GRI mechanism, e.g., only the backward reaction unfixes the nitrogen from the initiation species N_2 and, therefore initiates the reaction path (# Thermal: [[],[177],[]]).
4. **reaction mechanism file:** File of the reaction mechanism that has been used for the flame simulation (e.g.: GRI, GDF-Kin,...)

In the next step, the data of the flame simulation is stored in a dictionary. After this, the time vector is calculated in a function according to 3.14 and also put in the dictionary for the flame simulation data. Then, the inputs from the setup file and the sub-mechanism file are loaded from the files and stored in a dictionary for the inputs. As for the last input file, it is loaded and initialized by *Cantera*. After the reaction mechanism is set, the algorithm has access to chemical kinetics. This way, the next function can find all initiation reactions that unfix the tracing element from the initiation species in the reaction mechanism and store them in a list in the input dictionary. Following this, the undefined sub-mechanism is established by comparing initiation reactions from the sub-mechanisms with the list of all initiation reactions. In the next steps, the intermediate species are searched for in the reaction mechanism, and lists for the reactions between the species are created. In the nested lists for the reactions between species, the reactions are sorted, so that the information on intermediate reactant and product is kept for each reaction.

3.2.2 Pre-calculations

In the pre-calculation of the program, the algorithm calculates all fluxes that are fully determined by the inputs (species, reactions, state of gas). Hence, they are fixed values and do not change in the iterative process of the reaction path analysis. The execution of pre-calculation is demonstrated in flow chart 3.6.

The first assignments of the pre-calculations, define the basic settings of the iteration through the flame positions (start, stop, and stepsize). As a default, the iteration starts at position zero and ends at the end of the flame simulation. With a default value of 1 for the stepsize, every flame position

from the simulation is being analyzed. For coarser or partial analyses these values have to be adjusted. After this, the matrices for the fluxes and the pools are initialized and sized to fit all fluxes between intermediate species for all analyzed flame positions and in the case of the initiation fluxes also for every sub-mechanism.

Furthermore, two counters are set: One keeps track of the current flame position so that the correct simulation data is chosen for the calculations and the other counts the iterations.

The first step in the iteration through the flame positions is to set the state for the gas with the data from the simulation (temperature, pressure, and composition). The state of the gas is needed for the calculation of the fluxes using *Cantera*.

The function for the global fluxes calculates all net fluxes between the intermediate species for the current flame position. Here the net rates of progress for the reactions and the stoichiometric coefficients of the intermediate species are provided by *Cantera*. The net fluxes are then calculated for each pair of the species according to 2.20 and summed over the corresponding reactions between the species (2.21). Afterward, the global fluxes for the current flame position are saved as an entry in the matrix for all flame positions.

The next function calculates the initiation fluxes between the species for each sub-mechanism. The required rates and coefficients are again provided by *Cantera*. Opposed to the calculations of the global fluxes, for some reaction equations only the forward or backward reaction is considered in the calculation. The requested direction for the initiation is determined by the user in the sub-mechanism input file. And again, the fluxes for the current flame position are saved in the matrix for the whole flame.

The last function of this section calculates the pools for each species at the current flame position according to 3.12. As the current time step is required for the calculation, it is assigned before. The net fluxes or respectively the sources are also returned since they are needed later to state the flux cases and for the calculation of the allocation factors. Both pools and net fluxes are saved in matrices for the entire flame. Finally, the counters are updated before the next iteration.

3.2.3 Analysis

In the actual analysis part, the algorithm allocates the global fluxes and pools to the sub-mechanisms for all requested flame positions. The allocated fluxes determine the target fluxes. The entry condition for the while loop is the convergence criterion.

Figure 3.7 yields the initializations for the RPA. At first, the matrices for the allocation factors, allocated fluxes, and target fluxes are initialized. Here

start	$\leftarrow 0$	# Set start position in flame iteration
stop	$\leftarrow \text{length}(x)$	# Set end position in flame iteration)
step	$\leftarrow 1$	# Set step size in flame iteration
global_fluxes	$\leftarrow \text{zero-matrix}$	# Initialize global fluxes
ini_fluxes	$\leftarrow \text{zero-matrix}$	# Initialize initiation fluxes
pool	$\leftarrow \text{zero-matrix}$	# Initialize pools
total_fluxes_net	$\leftarrow \text{zero-matrix}$	# Initialize total net fluxes
flpos	$\leftarrow \text{start}$	# Initialize counter for flame positions
i	$\leftarrow 0$	# Initialize counter for iterations
For each flame position [start:stop:step]		
	SetState(gas,flame_dict,flpos)	# Sets gas state for the current flame position
	dt[i]	$\leftarrow t[\text{flpos}+1] - t[\text{flpos}]$ # Determine time step
	global_fluxes_flpos	$\leftarrow \text{CalcGlobalFluxes}(\text{gas}, \text{int_species}, \text{int_reactions}, \text{reactions_between_species})$ # Calculates global fluxes for current flame position
	global_fluxes[:,i]	$\leftarrow \text{global_fluxes_flpos}$ # Stores results in matrix
	ini_fluxes_flpos	$\leftarrow \text{CalcIniFluxes}(\text{gas}, \text{int_species}, \text{int_reactions}, \text{reactions_between_species})$ # Calculates initiation fluxes for current flame position
	ini_fluxes[:,i]	$\leftarrow \text{ini_fluxes_flpos}$ # Stores results in matrix
	pool_contribuion_flpos, total_fluxes_net_flpos	$\leftarrow \text{CalcPool}(\text{global_fluxes_flpos}, \text{int_species}, \text{dt})$ # Calculates the contributions to the pools of the species and the total net fluxes
	pool[:,i]	$\leftarrow \text{pool} + \text{pool_contribuion_flpos}$ # Add contributions to the pool
	total_fluxes_net[:,i]	$\leftarrow \text{total_fluxes_net_flpos}$ # Stores results in matrix
	flpos	$\leftarrow \text{flpos} + \text{step}$ # Set counter to next position in the flame
	i	$\leftarrow \text{flpos} + 1$ # Count iterations

Fig. 3.6: Flow chart for the pre-calculations of the SMART algorithm

all values from the current iteration are saved before the next iteration starts. After this, the flux correction factor is set for the first iteration. The initial guess is that all sub-mechanisms contribute equally to the formation of all species. To fulfill the entrance condition of the while loop, the residual is set to 1. The last assignment initializes the counter for the outer loop.

Figure 3.7 demonstrates the iterative approach of the reaction path analysis. The assignments and functions inside the outer while loop are repeated while

allocation_factors ← zero-matrix # Initialize matrix
allocated_pools ← zero-matrix # Initialize matrix
target_fluxes ← zero-matrix # Initialize matrix
fcf ← $\frac{1}{n_submech}$ * all-ones-matrix # Initialize flux correction factor
rpa_residual ← 1 # Initialize residual to enter iteration
rpa_it ← 0 # Initialize counter for iterations

Fig. 3.7: Flow chart for the initialization of the analysis

the convergence criteria is not met. Hence, the calculated residual must be smaller than the tolerance (user's input) to exit the loop. Inside the while loop is a for loop that again iterates through all requested flame positions.

Before the analysis for each flame-position starts the updated matrices for allocation factors allocated pools, and target fluxes are initialized. The updated values will be stored here. The counters for the flame positions and the iterations are initialized as well.

Then the iteration through the flame position starts by entering the for-loop. Again, the gas state for the current flame position is set, like in the pre-calculations. Then, the global fluxes are allocated with the help of the allocation factors. A further description of the process is demonstrated in figure 3.10. The allocated fluxes and the allocation factors are returned by the function and stored afterward. The next function allocates the pools to the sub-mechanisms according to subsection 3.1.4 for the current position in the flame. The results are stored in the corresponding matrix. Lastly, the counters are updated.

After the results for the allocation factors and allocated fluxes as well as pools are determined for all flame positions, the target fluxes are obtained from the allocated fluxes by calculating the net production rates for the target species sub-mechanism-wise. The sum of the target fluxes from the sub-mechanisms should equal the net production rate for the target species provided by *Cantera*. The following function updates the flux correction factor for the next iteration according to 3.19. After this, the residual for the reaction path analysis is calculated by comparing the updated results of the allocation factors, allocated pools, and target fluxes to the results of the previous iteration. A further explanation of the procedure is provided in section 3.3. Finally, the updated results are saved over the previous and the counter for the outer loop is updated.

The last assignments for the algorithm are illustrated in figure 3.9. All dictionaries for the input plus the results for the various fluxes, pools, allocation factors, flux correction factors, and residuals are combined in an output dictionary which is saved afterward as a file in the current directory.

Fig. 3.8: Flow chart for the analysis of the SMART algorithm

<code>outputs_dict ← inputs_dict, flame_dict, results # Combines all inputs and results in a dictionary</code>
<code>output-file ← outputs_dict # Save outputs from dictionary in pkl.-file</code>

Fig. 3.9: Flow chart for the output of the SMART algorithm

3.2.4 Allocating fluxes

The sub-program for the allocation of the fluxes from figure 3.7 is illustrated in greater detail in figure 3.10. The iterative procedure holds four nested loops. Two while-loops control the convergence of the allocated fluxes where one looks at the residual for each sub-mechanism and the other considers the overall residual for the entire set of allocated fluxes. Whereas one of the for-loops iterates through the sub-mechanism, and within this loop, the other analysis each intermediate species.

The first action is to initialize the allocated fluxes matrix for the current flame position with the corresponding initiation fluxes. The fluxes are obtained from the initiation reactions and are singular to a sub-mechanisms. Consequently, they are the initial values for the iterative process of the reaction path analysis for each sub-mechanism.

The next steps assign the convergence criteria due to a condition. If the counter for the iteration of the reaction path analysis is zero, meaning that no full RPA has been conducted yet, the tolerances are loose. For the first run through the flux correction factors are an initial guess and do not reflect the actual contributions of the sub-mechanism to the formation of a species, which might compromise the convergence. After the first iteration, the flux correction factors are computed by a routine, and the criteria tighten for the successive iterations. The maximum values for the iteration prevent infinite loops if errors in the simulation or setup inhibit convergence.

The following assignments initialize the residual and the counter for the outer loop. After entering, the current values for the allocated fluxes are saved on another matrix for the calculation of the residual. Afterward, the allocation for each sub-mechanism starts. On that account, the algorithm computes the allocation factors for each species according to subsection 3.1.3 with the help of the allocated sources (subsection 3.1.4). The net fluxes and the pools determine the flux case (subsection 3.1.2) for that matter. The function returns the allocation factor for a species and, subsequently, the next sub-program allocates the outflow fluxes for the considered species (subsection 3.1.1). After looping through species, the residual for the examined sub-mechanism is calculated, and the counter is updated. When every sub-mechanism reached convergence, the overall residual for the flame position is determined, and

Fig. 3.10: Flow chart of the function for the allocation of fluxes of the SMART algorithm

the counter for the outer while loop is updated. Further explanations on the calculation of the residuals follow in section 3.3.

3.3 Convergence

For a successful reaction path analysis, not only the allocated fluxes for each flame position have to reach convergence but also the results of the overall process have to show a consistent behavior so that the changes from one iteration to another lie within the required tolerance.

The first iterative procedure for allocating the fluxes with its corresponding convergence criteria is revealed by figure 3.8, where the residuals are calculated according to the residual norm of the relative change in the fluxes for a single sub-mechanism

$$\epsilon_{\Gamma,k,n}^{it+1} = \frac{\|\Gamma_{k,n}^{it+1} - \Gamma_{k,n}^{it}\|}{\|\Gamma_{k,n}^{it}\|} \quad (3.20)$$

and for all sub-mechanisms

$$\epsilon_{\Gamma,n}^{it+1} = \frac{\|\Gamma_n^{it+1} - \Gamma_n^{it}\|}{\|\Gamma_n^{it}\|}. \quad (3.21)$$

Here Γ is the matrix holding all allocated fluxes. The subscript k corresponds to the sub-mechanism and n is the position in the flame. The superscript it belongs to the iteration of the respective loop. The tolerances are set to 10^{-6} and 10^{-5} after the first attempt of a full reaction path analysis. The chosen values ensure smooth curves even for small fluxes and support a good convergence behavior for the overall analysis. Weaker criteria, however, allow much faster results, especially for kinetic reaction mechanisms with a large number of species. This is due to the nested loops where the inner loop iterates for each sub-mechanism through all intermediate species.

The convergence of the overall RPA (figure 3.8) is monitored by the maximum value of three different residuals calculated from the allocation factors H , the allocated pools Λ , and the target fluxes Θ . Again, the residuals are expressed as the norm of relative changes from the current to the previous iteration of the respective loop. Opposite to residuals above the convergence throughout the entire flame is considered.

$$\epsilon_{H,k}^{it+1} = \frac{\|H_k^{it+1} - H_k^{it}\|}{\|H_k^{it}\|} \quad (3.22)$$

$$\epsilon_{\Lambda,k}^{it+1} = \frac{\|\Lambda_k^{it+1} - \Lambda_k^{it}\|}{\|\Lambda_k^{it}\|} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\epsilon_{\Theta,k}^{it+1} = \frac{\|\Theta_k^{it+1} - \Theta_k^{it}\|}{\|\Theta_k^{it}\|} \quad (3.24)$$

Figure 3.11 shows the residuals for allocation factors, allocated pools and target fluxes for every sub-mechanisms over ten iterations. Here the different colored lines represent the residuals for the distinct sub-mechanisms, while the dashed black line is the tolerance. For this example, the analysis was carried out for ten iterations and not until the convergence criteria were met. The SMART algorithm shows an overall good convergence behavior for the considered application. It is evident, however, that the sub-mechanisms behave differently. Especially for the residuals of the target fluxes and the allocated pools, the undefined sub-mechanisms convergence more slowly compared to others. For a well-defined analysis, the formation of the target species due to undefined reaction paths should be close to zero. Therefore, the fluxes of the undefined sub-mechanisms are often very small and negligible. Figure 3.12 shows on the left the rate of production for an undefined mechanism (gray line) and on the right the comparison to the total rate of production (black dashed line) for the discussed analysis. Albeit the considered mechanisms takes part in the production of the target species NO, the contribution is very small compared to the total. To avoid irrelevant iterations and to ultimately save computational time, sub-mechanisms with an insignificant impact on the results are excluded from the convergence criterion. As stated before, the crucial residual for the analysis is the maximum of the residuals above,

$$\epsilon_{max}^{it+1} = \max(\epsilon_{H,k}^{it+1}, \epsilon_{\Lambda,k}^{it+1}, \epsilon_{\Theta,k}^{it+1}), \quad (3.25)$$

with the added exception that only residuals from sub-mechanisms with a bigger contribution than 0.1% to the formation of any intermediate species are taken into account. This threshold is also a user's input and can be edited concerning the purpose of the analysis and the application. The overall contribution to the formation of an intermediate species by a sub-mechanism is expressed by the flux correction factor (3.19).

Figure 3.13 compares the convergence for different equivalence ratios for premixed methane flames for the GRI mechanism. All conducted RPAs reach convergence within a maximum of eight iterations when the tolerance is set to 10^{-5} . Also, it is revealed that for the analyzed equivalence ratios from 0.7 to 1.3, the lean up to the stoichiometric flames converge faster than the rich flames where the former need five or six iterations while the latter require eight. The next figure 3.14 shows the convergence for four different kinetic reaction mechanisms for the same set up of a lean premixed methane flame.

Fig. 3.11: Residuals for allocation factors, allocated pools and target fluxes over ten iterations for a lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flame (GRI)

The UCSD mechanism converges first after four iterations, followed by the GRI and the GDF with 6 iterations. The Konnov mechanism needs more than twice the amount of iteration and hits the criterion after 14 iterations. The rising

Fig. 3.12: NO rate of production of undefined sub-mechanism compared to total rate of production for a lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flame (GRI)

Fig. 3.13: Maximum residuals for premixed methane flames with different equivalence ratios (GRI)

number of required iterations correlates with the size of the NO formation sub-model within the considered reaction mechanisms. The more detailed the NO formation in species and reaction the more iterations require the RPA to converge. Table 3.1 holds the number of intermediate species and reactions between the species for the respective kinetic reaction mechanism.

Figure 3.15 reveals the execution time for the SMART algorithm over 15

Fig. 3.14: Maximum residuals for lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flames for different kinetic reaction mechanisms

Tab. 3.1: Intermediate species and reactions for analysed kinetic reaction mechanisms (UCSD, GRI, GDF, Konnov)

	Intermediate species	Reactions between interm. species
UCSD	15	53
GRI	18	108
GDF	22	187
Konnov	37	455

iterations for the UCSD, the GRI, the GDF, and the Konnov mechanism. It is evident that the convergence time not only depends on the number of iterations required but also on the size of the mechanisms. An increasing amount of species and reactions leads to a rising amount of time per iteration so that the time curves steepen from the smallest to the biggest mechanism. Additionally, the blow-up shows that the iterative process of the analysis has different starting times which represent the time required for the pre-processing and pre-calculations (pre-analysis). Again, the different amount of time correlates with the size of the NO sub-model. An overview of the time required for the pre-analysis, the analysis, and the meantime for one iteration is given in table 3.2.

In summary, the investigations on the progress of residuals state that the

Fig. 3.15: Execution time for lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flames for different kinetic reaction mechanisms

Tab. 3.2: Execution time of the pre-analysis (pre-processing and pre-calculations), the analysis and the mean time for one iteration of the analysis.

	Pre-Analysis [s]	Analysis [s]	Mean per Iteration [s]
UCSD	1.4	59.4	12.1
GRI	2.1	252.2	30.3
GDF	4.2	453.7	76.8
Konnov	11.8	2229.9	148.8

established criteria ensure convergence within a reasonable amount of iterations for all relevant sub-mechanism of a reaction path analysis for the considered applications. The amount of required iterations depends on the flame (here: equivalence ratio) and the kinetic reaction mechanism. Furthermore, the required iterations as well as the size of the reaction mechanism have a high impact on the convergence time.

4 Comparison of reaction path analysis methods

The objective of this chapter is to evaluate the results of the SMART algorithm. Therefore, results from the SMART algorithm are compared to another reaction path analysis from the literature. A detailed analysis of the kinetics allows insights into the benefits and limitations of the approaches.

In previous studies of NO formation, several methods of reaction path analysis were used to extract the contributions of distinct mechanisms to the formation of NO throughout the flame. In general, there are two strategies:

For the first strategy, the focus is based on NO related reactions. These reactions are grouped to the specified formation mechanisms (Thermal, N_2O , NNH, etc.) and the respective contributions are identified by the summation of the reactions' NO productions. For small kinetic mechanisms, this is a relatively easy post-processing analysis, but as the mechanisms grow and become more complex, this approach yields difficulties. Furthermore, some pathways are coupled through shared reactions. Hence, a fixed attribution to a single mechanism causes overprediction, respectively underprediction.

The other main approach is based on the circumstance that NO_x chemistry usually has a neglectable effect on the flame structure and temperature [17]. Therefore, parts of the NO_x chemistry can be removed from the kinetic mechanism. Consequently, the flame simulation has to be repeated for the RPA with altered NO_x subsets to extract the desired contributions from the formation pathways. The advantage of this approach is that in general, only the initiation reactions, which are more clearly established for the distinct routes as the NO related reactions, have to be removed. Anyhow, the accuracy of these RPAs applies only to the extent that species concentrations from the altered mechanisms do not significantly retard or accelerate the kinetics of the remaining pathways [34].

Nishioka et al.[36] proposed a reaction path analysis that couples the two main approaches described above. Here the thermal contribution is extracted by an additional simulation. The NO_x related species and reactions that are not involved in the Thermal route are removed from the kinetic mechanisms. Accordingly, the remaining species from the NO_x sub-model are N, NO, and N_2 . As for the reactions, only the initiation reaction and the follow-up reactions were maintained: Apart from the Thermal, also the N_2O , the NO₂ net, and the

Prompt route were extracted. Here, the N_2O and the NO_2 net mechanism were obtained by establishing the corresponding NO related reactions and summing up their NO production rates obtained from simulation results from the full mechanisms. Finally, the Prompt mechanism is obtained by subtracting the summation of the above three mechanisms from the calculations of the full mechanism simulation.

E.-S. Cho and S.H. Chung [8] executed a reaction path analysis that is based on the approach from Nishioka et al. The objective of this new method was to avoid interference in the Thermal mechanism caused by the removal of the remaining NOx chemistry. The Thermal mechanism is here obtained with the same strategy as the other mechanisms, namely by the summation of a set of reactions, comprising the initiation reaction and the two follow-up reactions. This way the RPA is solely post-processing. The contributions of all other routes are identified exactly as described by Nishioka et al. This way, the results for the N_2O and NO_2 net are identical. Only Thermal and Prompt contributions differ due to the modified approach for the Thermal and the dependence from the Prompt on the results of the other mechanisms.

Guo et al. [17] proposed a method that determines the contributions of the chemical routes of NO formation from Thermal, Prompt, N_2O and NNH by progressively removing the corresponding initiation reaction. The differences between the calculations are then attributed to the considered mechanism. The order of removal is a crucial factor regarding the results of the RPA. Guo et al. starts with the removal of the Prompt initiation and then further removes NNH and lastly N_2O initiation reactions. The determination of the Thermal contribution differs since it is not obtained by a difference but from the last simulation where all initiation reactions from the other mechanisms are removed.

A similar method was executed by S. Naik and N. Laurendeau [34]. In this work, only the initiation reactions from a single sub-mechanism are removed from the reaction mechanism for the simulation of each subset. Consequently, the contribution of each chemical route is obtained by subtracting the production of the subset from the full mechanism's production. This way each sub-mechanism requires a flame simulation.

Table 4.1 gives an overview of all presented reaction path analysis.

4.1 Approach

The results of the SMART algorithm are compared to the results of the RPA proposed by S. Naik and N. Laurendeau [34]. In the following referred to as the subtraction method. This RPA, like the SMART, focuses on the initiation reactions to extract the pathways. By removing only the initial reaction from

Tab. 4.1: Summary of reaction path analysis methods

	Nishioka et al. [36]	E.-S. Cho and S.H. Chung [8]	Guo et al. [17]	S. Naik and N. Laurendau [34]
Thermal	Total production from simulation with Thermal subset: $NO + N \rightleftharpoons N_2 + O$ (R178) $N + O_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + O$ (R179) $N + OH \rightleftharpoons NO + H$ (R180) (other NOx reactions are removed)	Full kinetic mechanism Summation of productions by Thermal mechanism: $NO + N \rightleftharpoons N_2 + O$ (R178) $N + O_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + O$ (R179) $N + OH \rightleftharpoons NO + H$ (R180)	Total production from flame simulation with subset mechanism: Prompt, NNH and N2O initiation removed. (see below for reaction equations) Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without Prompt (see above) and NNH initiation reactions: $NH + N \rightleftharpoons N_2 + H$ (R191) $NH + NO \rightleftharpoons N_2 + OH$ (R198) $NNH \rightleftharpoons N_2 + H$ (R204) $NNH + M \rightleftharpoons N_2 + H + M$ (R205) $NNH + O_2 \rightleftharpoons HO_2 + N_2$ (R206) $NNH + O \rightleftharpoons OH + N_2$ (R207) $NNH + H \rightleftharpoons H_2 + N_2$ (R209) $NNH + OH \rightleftharpoons H_2O + N_2$ (R210)	Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without Thermal initiation reaction: $NO + N \rightleftharpoons N_2 + O$ (R178) Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without NNH initiation reaction: $NNH + O \rightleftharpoons NH + NO$ (R208)
NNH				
N2O	Summation of productions by N2O mechanism: $N_2O + O \rightleftharpoons 2 NO$ (R182) $N_2O + H \rightleftharpoons NH + NO$ (R199) $N_2O + CO \rightleftharpoons NCO + NO$ (R228) (Full kinetic mechanisms)	Summation of productions by N2O mechanism: $N_2O + O \rightleftharpoons 2 NO$ (R182) $N_2O + H \rightleftharpoons NH + NO$ (R199) $N_2O + CO \rightleftharpoons NCO + NO$ (R228) (Full kinetic mechanisms)	Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without Prompt (see above), NNH (see above) and N2O initiation reactions: $N_2O + O \rightleftharpoons N_2 + O_2$ (R181) $N_2O + O + O \rightleftharpoons 2 NO$ (R182) $N_2O + H \rightleftharpoons N_2 + OH$ (R183) $N_2O + OH \rightleftharpoons N_2 + HO_2$ (R184) $N_2O (+M) \rightleftharpoons N_2 + O (+M)$ (R185)	Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without N2O initiation reaction: $N_2O + O \rightleftharpoons N_2 + O_2$ (R181) $N_2O + O + O \rightleftharpoons 2 NO$ (R182) $N_2O + H \rightleftharpoons N_2 + OH$ (R183) $N_2O + OH \rightleftharpoons N_2 + HO_2$ (R184) $N_2O (+M) \rightleftharpoons N_2 + O (+M)$ (R185)
NO2	Summation of productions by NO2 mechanism: $HO_2 + NO \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + OH$ (R186) $NO + O + M \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + M$ (R187) $NO_2 + O \rightleftharpoons NO + O_2$ (R188) $H + NO_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + OH$ (R189) $NO_2 + CN \rightleftharpoons NCO + NO$ (R281) (Full kinetic mechanism)	Summation of productions by NO2 mechanism: $HO_2 + NO \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + OH$ (R186) $NO + O + M \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + M$ (R187) $NO_2 + O \rightleftharpoons NO + O_2$ (R188) $H + NO_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + OH$ (R189) $NO_2 + CN \rightleftharpoons NCO + NO$ (R281) (Full kinetic mechanism)	Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without Prompt initiation reaction: $CH + N_2 \rightleftharpoons HCN + N$ (R240)	Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without Prompt initiation reaction: $CH + N_2 \rightleftharpoons HCN + N$ (R240)
Prompt	Difference between total productions and the summation of productions from Thermal, N2O and NO2 routes	Difference between total productions and the summation of productions from Thermal, N2O and NO2 routes	Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without Prompt initiation reaction: $CH + N_2 \rightleftharpoons HCN + N$ (R240)	Difference between full kinetic mechanism and subset mechanism without Prompt initiation reaction: $CH + N_2 \rightleftharpoons HCN + N$ (R240)

the currently analyzed route, the changes to the NO_x model in the kinetic reaction set are as small as possible. Furthermore, the subtraction method does not force the results of the RPA to match the total NO formation. The RPAs proposed by Nishioka et al. or E.-S. Cho and S.H. Chung define Prompt NO as the difference between the total NO formation and the contributions of the other analyzed mechanisms. This approach yields the compromise that all inaccuracies from the analyzed pathways are attributed to the remaining, namely the Prompt mechanism.

The basic setup for the comparison is a premixed methane-air flame at ambient pressure and with an inlet temperature of 300 K. The GRI is the kinetic reaction mechanisms in the simulation.

The SMART algorithm conducts a reaction path analysis for the mechanisms listed in the table 4.2. Here the NNX links the sub-mechanisms N₂O and NNH. Next to the names of the considered pathways are the corresponding initiation reactions with the respective numbers of the GRI mechanism.

The algorithm establishes for the NO production two further sub-mechanisms. The first is the *N2 undefined* sub-mechanism which includes all yet unassigned nitrogen unfixing reactions. The second is the *NO undefined* sub-mechanisms which contains all reactions that convert NO back to any intermediate species and that have not been used to describe any other sub-mechanism. The *NO undefined* is needed, since sub-mechanisms, like the Reburn, initiate the depletion of NO. Anyhow, for the current analysis both undefined sub-mechanisms are close to zero and, therefore, not further discussed. As for the basic setup of the SMART algorithm, the following inputs are supplied:

- initiation species: N₂
- tracking element species: N
- target species: NO
- RPA tolerance: 10⁻⁶
- threshold: 10⁻³

The determination of the sub-mechanisms' contributions is executed as described in the previous section.

For the subtraction method, the pathways are determined as described in table 4.1. Opposed to the SMART algorithm, this approach only yields solutions for the main formation pathways Thermal, Prompt, and NNX. To compare all relevant mechanisms, the subtraction method is extended in this work. The minor mechanisms NO₂, HNO, and Reburn are extracted according to the fundamental idea of the approach. The initiation reactions, that are

Tab. 4.2: Initiation reactions for the SMART analysis using the GRI-Mech 3.0

Sub-mechanism	Reaction equation	Reaction #
Thermal	$NO + N \leftarrow N_2 + O$	R178
NNX	$N_2O + O \leftarrow N_2 + O_2$	R181
	$N_2O + H \leftarrow N_2 + OH$	R183
	$N_2O + OH \leftarrow N_2 + HO_2$	R184
	$N_2O (+M) \leftarrow N_2 + O (+M)$	R185
	$NNH \leftarrow N_2 + H$	R204
	$NNH + M \leftarrow N_2 + H + M$	R205
	$NNH + O_2 \leftarrow HO_2 + N_2$	R206
	$NNH + O \leftarrow OH + N_2$	R207
	$NNH + H \leftarrow H_2 + N_2$	R209
	$NNH + OH \leftarrow H_2O + N_2$	R210
Prompt	$H_2CN + N \leftarrow N_2 + CH_2$	R238
	$C + N_2 \rightarrow CN + N$	R239
	$CH + N_2 \rightarrow HCN + N$	R249
	$CH + N_2 (+M) \rightarrow HCNN (+M)$	R241
	$CH_2 + N_2 \rightarrow HCN + NH$	R242
	$CH_2(S) + N_2 \rightarrow NH + HCN$	R243
	$HCNN + H \leftarrow CH_2 + N_2$	R261
NO2	$HO_2 + NO \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + OH$	R186
	$NO + O + M \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + M$	R187
	$NO_2 + O \rightleftharpoons NO + O_2$	R188
	$H + NO_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + OH$	R189
HNO	$H + NO + M \rightleftharpoons HNO + M$	R212
	$HNO + O \rightleftharpoons NO + OH$	R213
	$H + HNO \rightleftharpoons H_2 + NO$	R214
	$HNO + OH \rightleftharpoons H_2O + NO$	R215
	$HNO + O_2 \rightleftharpoons HO_2 + NO$	R216
Reburn	$NCO + NO \rightarrow N_2O + CO$	R228
	$NCO + NO \rightarrow N_2 + CO_2$	R229
	$C + NO \rightarrow CN + O$	R244
	$C + NO \rightarrow CO + N$	R245
	$CH + NO \rightarrow HCN + O$	R246
	$CH + NO \rightarrow H + NCO$	R247
	$CH + NO \rightarrow HCO + N$	R248
	$CH_2 + NO \rightarrow H + HNCO$	R249
	$CH_2 + NO \rightarrow HCN + OH$	R250
	$CH_2 + NO \rightarrow H + HCNO$	R251
	$CH_2(S) + NO \rightarrow H + HNCO$	R252
	$CH_2(S) + NO \rightarrow HCN + OH$	R253
	$CH_2(S) + NO \rightarrow H + HCNO$	R254
	$CH_3 + NO \rightarrow H_2O + HCN$	R255
	$CH_3 + NO \rightarrow H_2CN + OH$	R256
	$HCNN + O \leftarrow HCN + NO$	R258
	$HCCO + NO \rightarrow HCNO$	R274
	$CN + NO_2 \leftarrow NCO + NO$	R281

removed from the kinetic mechanism, are the same as described in table 4.2. Note that for this RPA, both directions of the reactions are removed to preserve consistency. In summary, the subtraction method requires the following flame simulations for this application:

1. Full kinetic mechanism
2. Thermal initiation removed
3. NNH initiation removed
4. N_2O initiation removed
5. Prompt initiation removed
6. NO_2 net initiation removed
7. HNO initiation removed
8. Reburn initiation removed

The analyses are conducted for a range of equivalence ratios. The equivalence ratio has a very significant impact on the relative importance of the distinct formation routes regarding the total NO production. The reaction path analyses should capture the changes in the pathways due to the variation in the combustion condition. The figure shows the relative contributions of sub-mechanisms to the overall formed NO in the flame for increasing ratios. The relative contributions are obtained from an RPA by the SMART algorithm.

Fig. 4.1: Relative contributions to the total formation of NO for a premixed methane flame in dependence of the equivalence ratio (GRI-Mech 3.0)

The results from this analysis agree with the stated characteristic of sub-mechanisms (section 2.2) and show for the main formation pathways the

same approximate distribution over the equivalence ratios as illustrated in the literature (figure 1.1). The Thermal formation path is most relevant for slightly lean and stoichiometric flames and becomes irrelevant for rather rich flames since it goes almost zero for an equivalence ratio of 1.3. The NNX loses importance with rising equivalence ratios and also ends close to zero for ϕ equals 1.3. However, for the leanest condition, the NNX surpasses the contribution of the Thermal. The Prompt mechanism gains rapidly in importance for rich flames. But also for lean flames, the mechanism contributes steadily almost 20% to the formation of NO. The NO2 mechanism is least notable to the overall formation of NO. Its impact rises with increasing lean and rich flames. For stoichiometric conditions, the relative contribution is close to zero. The HNO mechanism is second to the Prompt for the two richest conditions. The Reburn, like the Prompt gains significance as the flames, become richer due to its dependence on C-N radicals and reaches a relative contribution of almost 40 % to the depletion of NO.

Lastly, the effects of the kinetic mechanism on the quality of results for the RPAs are examined. Here the boundary conditions for the flame remain, but this time the simulations are executed using the GDF mechanism. The initiation reaction for the SMART algorithm can be found in the appendix A. For the subtraction method the following reactions have been removed:

The results for all applications are compared regarding the NO production rates and the contribution to the total NO formation. For the SMART algorithm, the calculated target fluxes are the respective rate of productions and the contributions are obtained by integrating the rate of productions (ROP) according to

$$X_{NO,k} = \frac{R_\infty T}{p} \int \text{ROP}_k dt. \quad (4.1)$$

Here R_∞ is the universal gas constant and T and p are the temperature and pressure through the flame. This approach is limited to the extent that the algorithm does not account directly for diffusion. Integrating through the entire flame, however, should yield a very good estimation regarding the number of molecules produced in the flame. For the subtraction method, the differences in the simulations for the total rate of productions and the molar fractions of NO at the end of the flame are attributed to the respective route as production rates and contributions to the formation.

4.2 Results and discussion

This chapter presents and compares the results from the reaction path analyses conducted with the help of the subtraction method and the SMART algorithm. First, the NO production rates for each sub-mechanisms are compared for a single application to analyze the underlying causes of the deviations. Secondly, the resulting total NO formations for the application are examined to validate the accuracy of the RPAs. The next part investigates the solutions of the reaction path analyses over a range of equivalence ratios to estimate the influence on the quality of the results. Lastly, the results for a further kinetic mechanism demonstrate the impact of the alteration on the accuracy of predictions.

4.2.1 NO rates of production for the analysed pathways

Figure 4.3 reveals the complete results from the subtraction method and for the SMART algorithm showing the NO rates of production for each analyzed pathway. Supplementary, the figure 4.2 shows the concentrations of selected radicals in the flame while figure 4.4 provides a more detailed view of the comparison of each pathway.

Fig. 4.2: Concentration of selected radicals for a slightly lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flame (GRI-Mech 3.0)

Looking at the main formation pathways, the production rates expose in general a similar behavior for the compared RPAs. The Prompt pathways exhibit

Fig. 4.3: Reaction path analyses using the subtraction method (top) and the SMART algorithm (bottom) for a slightly lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flame (GRI-Mech 3.0)

rapid productions of NO in the reaction zone due to the high concentration of CH radicals while the formations due to NNX and Thermal are initiated afterward profiting from the rising concentration of O. The NNX rising steeper as the slow Thermal depends on higher temperatures and is, therefore, leading towards the end of the flame.

The first deviations between the predicted formation routes are visible in the small fluctuation in the preheat zone. The depletion of NO is caused by forward diffused NO that is converted to NO₂ due to the concentration of HO₂ radicals (R186). Afterward, NO₂ is reformed to NO since the concentrations for H and

Fig. 4.4: Comparison of the analysed pathways for the subtraction method and the SMART algorithm

O rise (R189) closer to the reaction zone as well as the temperature and NO_2 is not stable for high temperatures [40]. While both RPAs coherently attribute this ROP to the NO_2 pathway, the subtraction method also attributes shares of the ROP to the other mechanisms. The Prompt is the main contributor followed by the NNX. The Prompt as well as the NNX are major contributors to the NO formation in the reaction zone and, therefore, the source of the

diffused NO. The removal of the initiation reaction in the subset simulation leads to a decrease in the concentration of NO in the preheat zone. Hence, less NO is converted to NO₂ and vice versa. This difference in the simulation with the full kinetic mechanisms is then attributed to the pathway.

The direct comparisons for each chemical route reveal further deviations. For the Thermal, the SMART algorithm predicts an unexpected elevation of the NO production rate before the mechanism is initiated by reaction R178. This phenomenon is the consequence of the simplification to account for diffusion. Figure 4.5 shows the total net flux for the species N (blue dashed line) and the NO rate of production from the Thermal mechanism (blue solid line). The violet line represents the pool of the species N. As long as the pool and the total net flux of the species N are negative, the flux case III is active and indicates a forward diffusion of N in the flame. Due to the enduring production of N through the initial reaction of the Thermal, the mechanism is a major contributor to its overall formation. This is captured in the flux correction factor and leads to the assumption that a share of the diffused N has been produced by the Thermal mechanism. Consequently, the following conversion to NO is also allocated to the Thermal and generates the discussed elevation.

The subtraction method exhibits for the Thermal the small fluctuations in the

Fig. 4.5: Impact of the diffusion simplification on the Thermal route

beginning as explained before and then the result shows a massive depletion of NO resulting in a steeper rise of the rate and a small overshooting at the main production area around the peak location. This significant negative

low point means that the removal of the Thermal initiation from the kinetic mechanism has led to a higher total production rate in the flame simulation. This rise is caused by an acceleration of the kinetics from the Prompt route. Figure 4.6 yields the net rates of progress for the initial reaction of the Prompt mechanisms R240 (left) and the summation of net rates for the follow-up reactions of the Thermal mechanism. The removal of the Thermal initiation accelerates the Prompt mechanism and leads to a higher production rate of atomic nitrogen through R240. The nitrogen is then converted to NO by R179 and R180 and causes the unexpected depletion rate in the Thermal pathway. Similar plunges for the production rate are also exhibited in the NNX and

Fig. 4.6: Interference between the Prompt and the Thermal mechanism caused by the subtraction method

NO₂ net mechanism. For the former, the depletion is primarily caused by the N₂O mechanism. The removal of the respective initiation reaction causes in each simulation a heightened concentration of CH leading to the described acceleration of the Prompt mechanism. The locations in the flame, however, suggest the assumption that the depletions also correlate with the Reburn chemistry since its tight connection with the Prompt mechanism by C-N and amine radicals (NH, NH₂).

Apart from the observed plunge, the rates for the NNX mechanisms show deviations in peak values and the production downstream from the reaction zone. Similar behavior is also noticeable in the Prompt mechanism and around the positive peak of the Reburn. All three mechanisms are strongly interrelated by amine radicals which react with O, OH or O₂ to NO. The figure shows the change in NH concentrations due to the removal of the pathways' initiation reactions. As expected, the reduction in the kinetic mechanisms leads to a lower concentration of NH in the flame. This is not only causing a directly diminished rate of production for the NO by the conversion described above but

Fig. 4.7: NH concentrations for flame simulations with full and reduced kinetic mechanisms

also a subsequent decrease in production due to HNO. The HNO mechanism likewise depends on amine radicals as its formation includes the reactions below:

HNO is then converted by the reaction R181 - R185 to NO and vice versa. The SMART algorithm clearly shows that the conversion of HNO contributes to a considerable formation of NO for this application. Consequently, the results for the NNX, Prompt, and Reburn mechanism predict a higher production rate of NO as it comprises the actual contribution of the mechanism and its share of NO formation from the HNO mechanism. The attempt to extract the HNO mechanism from the NO formation with the subtraction method does not agree with the predictions of the SMART algorithm. The removal of its initiation reactions does not result in diminished NO production rate but in an acceleration of the related pathways. As a consequence, the RPA yields a NO depletion instead of a production rate in the reaction zone.

4.2.2 Total NO formation

The summation of the production rates from each pathway represents the total NO formation rate in the flame. Therefore it is supposed to match the NO rate of production (ROP) calculated by the Cantera simulation. Figure 4.8

Fig. 4.8: Comparison of total NO rate of productions from the reaction path analyses

compares the summed production rate as a total for the subtraction method (dashed-dotted line) and the SMART algorithm (dashed line) in the upper plot. The black circles represent the NO ROP calculated by Cantera. The total formation predicted by the SMART algorithm matches the ROP better than the total from the subtraction method. For the latter, the fluctuation in the pre-heat zone is overpredicted for the depletion as well as the formation of NO. In the reaction zone, the formation is underpredicted and the peak

production is slightly shifted while the post-flame formation rate is heightened. The lower plot of figure 4.8 reveals the absolute errors for both RPAs. Table 4.3 summarizes the errors. For the SMART, the maximum absolute error is in the magnitude of 10^{-5} so that no deviation is visible for this scale. The small integrated error additionally confirms the overall agreement of the ROPs. The subtraction method induces a very high absolute error manifested as a low point in the curve. The reason is the underprediction in the flame zone and the shift of the peaks. The calculations demonstrate that the absolute, as well as the integrated errors regarding the predicted rates and the actual rate, differ in the magnitude of 10^{-4} between the subtraction method and the SMART algorithm.

The errors in the total formation rate of the subtraction method are the consequence of the discussed problems in the extraction of the distinct pathways. The first fluctuations are due to the double accounting for the NO_2 net mechanism by the pathway itself and the contributions of the other mechanisms. The maximum deviation is the result of the observed depletion rates in the Thermal, NNX, and NO_2 net mechanism coupled with the slight shifts in the peaks. The increased post-flame production rate is most likely due to overprediction in the NO_2 , NNX, and Reburn mechanism. Since the double accounting due to the added extraction of the minor mechanisms (NO_2 , HNO, and Reburn) seems to have a significant impact on the quality of the results, the total formation rate due to the main pathways is also calculated and examined. Figure 4.9

Fig. 4.9: Impact of the minor pathways on the total NO rate of production calculated by the subtraction method

shows the total considering all pathways (gray dashed-dotted) line and the total for the main mechanism (pink dashed line) compared to the actual NO ROP. The errors in the pre-flame, reaction, and post-flame zone are diminished by the new total. The maximum error for the main mechanism total is $-0.181 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the integrated error is $0.0015 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Anyhow, it remains that the NO production rate is severely underpredicted in the reaction zone and overpredict for the entire post-flame region.

Another result of each analysis is the total formation of NO which is obtained from the concentration of NO at the end of the flame. The total formation is a consequence of the partial contributions from the analyzed pathway. Figure 4.10 summarizes the results. The best agreement scores the Thermal mecha-

Fig. 4.10: Comparison of contributions from the analysed pathways to the total NO formation

nisms. For both analyses, the Thermal is the main contributor to the total formation followed by NNX and Prompt. Due to the capturing of the HNO mechanism in the NNX, Prompt, and Reburn, all contributions reach higher values as obtained by the SMART algorithm. As a consequence of the unexpected behavior of the NO₂ mechanisms in the reaction zone and especially in the post-flame region, the concentrations disagree. For HNO, the subtraction method failed to produce convincing results, leading to high deviations in the NO formation. Again, the total of the pathways' contributions should match the total NO concentration calculated in the flame simulation. In this application total concentration is 38.54 ppm. The total NO formation scored by the SMART algorithm is very close to the actual NO concentration with a relative error of -0.024 %. The subtraction method predicts a significant heightened

concentration. The relative error is here 13.53 %. As discussed before, the high deviation is partly due to the double accounting. The summation of the NO formations from main formation pathways leads to total NO formation closer to the anticipated result. The relative error is reduced to 5.92 %.

Tab. 4.3: Summary of errors for the reaction path analyses

	Total rate of production		Total NO formation
	Max. abs. error [$\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{s}}$]	Integr. error [$\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3}$]	Rel. error [%]
Subtraction	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	13.53
Subtraction (Main Pathways)	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	5.92
SMART	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.024

4.2.3 Variation of equivalence ratios

Thermal

The results for the comparison of the Thermal NO production rates for a range of equivalence ratios are collected in figure 4.11. Each plot shows the rates for a different equivalence ratio, and within the plots, the light blue lines represent the results of the subtraction method, while the medium blue lines are the consequence of the analysis with the SMART algorithm.

The development of Thermal NO formation routes from the SMART algorithm reveals the following characteristics:

1. All productions rates show a steady behaviour.
2. The small rise in the production rate before the actual initiation correlates, as expected, with the importance of the Thermal regarding the overall NO formation (compare fig 4.1).
3. The rate of production increases from the leanest flame and reaches a maximum for the stoichiometric flame. After this, the rate decreases until it goes almost zero for the richest flame.
4. The mechanism has no negative rate of production of NO for any equivalence ratio.

The rates extracted by the subtraction method exhibit the following key characteristics:

1. The lean flames up to the slightly rich flame ($\phi=1.1$) show approximately the behaviour as previously discussed for the flame with $\phi=0.9$: Fluctuations in the beginning, a deep plunge in the reaction zone and an post-flame overprediction.

Fig. 4.11: Comparison of the Thermal NO rate of production for a range of equivalence ratios calculated by distinct the reaction path analyses

2. For the two leanest flames the overshooting in the peak area is more distinct.
3. The fluctuations increase with the equivalence ratio. For the progressing rich flames the fluctuations exceed the actual production rate

Figure 4.12 compares the peaks of Thermal NO production and reveals the relative errors in percent. The comparison only extends to an equivalence ratio of 1.1. For richer flames the subtraction method fails to convey a reliable production rate as the fluctuations predominate. The subtraction method predicts for all cases a higher peak value than the SMART algorithm. The peaks agree best for equivalence ratios with the highest production rates ($\phi=0.9$, $\phi=1.0$) and where Thermal NO is the major contribution to the total formation of NO (see figure 4.1). Here the relative error is around 5%. For conditions where Thermal NO is less important compared to other mechanisms the errors rapidly increase. For the leanest flame the relative error is already 28%.

Fig. 4.12: Comparison of the Thermal peak production for a range of equivalence rates determined by the distinct reaction path analyses

Figure 4.13 reveals the NO concentrations for both predictions at the end of flame. The results for the SMART algorithm were obtained by the integration

of the production rate while the results for the subtraction method are the difference between the calculated concentrations from both flame simulations. The relative error for the richest flame is not included as it exceeded 150%. The results for the concentrations show a better agreement than the results for the peak values with the best match for a lean flame ($\phi=0.8$). The relative error is less than 2%. Similar results are obtained for the next two flames ($\phi=0.9$, $\phi=1.0$).

Fig. 4.13: Comparison of Thermal contributions the total NO formation for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses

Regarding the predicted behaviour of the NO production rate and the errors in the peak values, the relatively good agreement of the total formation of NO is unexpected. However, the results of the subtraction method exhibit a significant depletion followed by a step rise of the production rate exceeding the peak values of the SMART so that the effects on the total NO concentration at the end of the flame cancel out.

NNX

Figure 4.14 yields the results for the comparison of the NO production rates for the NNX pathway. Each plot illustrates the rates for a different equivalence ratio. The orange lines originate from the analysis with the SMART algorithm, whereas the light orange lines represent the results of the subtraction method.

Fig. 4.14: Comparison of the NNX NO rate of production for a range of equivalence ratios calculated by the distinct reaction path analyses

Here the results for the NNH and the N₂O mechanism are summed to obtain the rate for NNX.

For the SMART algorithm the results reveal the following characteristics:

1. The peak production rate rises from the leanest to the stoichiometric flame and decreases with progressing richer flames.
2. The rates show for all ratios a steady behaviour with a similar shape. Though, the steep increase and decreases with declining intensity after the peak flattens for progressing rich flames.
3. The mechanism has no negative rate of production of NO for any equivalence ratio.

The results from the subtraction method show different behaviour:

1. The lean flames up to the stoichiometric flame show a similar behaviour as for the previously discussed flame with $\phi=0.9$: Fluctuations in the beginning, a deep plunge in the reaction zone and an post-flame overprediction.
2. For the slightly rich flame peak shows a significant shift to the right and is lower than the calculated peak from the SMART.
3. For the progressing rich flames the fluctuations predominate in extracted production rate.

The SMART algorithm provides consistent and reasonable results for all equivalence ratios while the subtraction method fails to convey reliable production rates, especially as the flames become richer. Figure 4.15 compares the peak values and shows the relative errors between the predictions up to an equivalence ratio of 1.1, as for richer flames the peaks are reached by the fluctuations. The values agree best for the stoichiometric flame. It is also the highest peak. The relative error is here 6.1 %. With decreasing peak values the relative errors between the the RPAs increase. As mentioned before, for the slightly rich flame the peak of the subtraction method is lower than the SMART peak.

Figure 4.15 compares the NO concentration provided by the considered pathways for both RPAs also including the relative errors. For lean up to the stoichiometric flame the subtraction method calculates a higher NO formation as the SMART algorithm. The relative errors are around 30 %. The best agreement is achieved for the slightly rich flame with an error of 6 %. For the progressing rich flames the results rapidly deteriorate. Considering the rate of productions, the results suggest the assumption that the relatively good agreement for the slightly rich flame is not due to actual better predictions but to the shift and the lower peak value. It does not testify an overall better

Fig. 4.15: Comparison of the NNX peak production rates for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses

accordance. Hence, the comparatively best and also reliable agreement is achieved for the leanest flame with an error of 28 %. Here the NNX mechanism is the main contributor to the total NO formation, cf. figure 4.1.

Prompt

The figure 4.17 summarizes the results for the comparison of the NO production rates for the Prompt pathway. Each plot demonstrates the rates for a different equivalence ratio. The green lines originate from the analysis with the SMART algorithm, whereas the light green lines represent the results of the subtraction method. The extracted production rates from the SMART algorithm deliver the following characteristics:

1. The peak production rate rises from the leanest to the second richest flame and decreases for the richest.
2. The rates show for all ratios a steady behaviour with a similar shape.

Fig. 4.16: Comparison of NNX contributions to the total NO formation for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses

3. The mechanism has no negative rate of production of NO for any equivalence ratio.

The results from the subtraction method reveal the following features:

1. The results show for all equivalence ratios a similar behaviour as previously discussed regarding the flame with $\phi=0.9$: Fluctuations in the beginning, an overpredicted peak in the reaction zone and a slight overprediction post-flame.
2. For progressing rich flames the shift to the right becomes more distinct as well as the heightened production rate in the post-flame region.
3. The rate develops an additional dip before the steep rise in the flame front as the flames become richer.

The SMART algorithm yields rate of productions with a comprehensible and consistent behaviour for the Prompt mechanism with rising peak values up to the second leanest flames as the availability of CH radicals increases. A similar behaviour is predicted by the subtraction method (apart from the fluctuations) though the peaks reach higher values. The differences for the peak values are exhibited in figure 4.18. Here the leanest and the richest flame show the best

Fig. 4.17: Comparison of the Prompt NO rate of production for a range of equivalence ratios calculated by the distinct reaction path analyses

Fig. 4.18: Comparison of the Prompt peak production rates for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses

agreements for the peak values. The errors then rise for both sides towards the stoichiometric flame, where the highest deviation with a relative error of 11.7 % is reached. Opposed to this, the deviations in the scored NO concentration show better accordance around the stoichiometric ratio and errors above 50 % for the leanest flames. Hence, the errors decrease with an increase of the produced NO, except for the richest flame. Here the contributions from the Thermal and the NNX to the total formation are almost zero. Considering the production rate, the discontinuation of the pathways seem to severely effect the Prompt mechanism extracted by subtraction method. The result shows for this application a considerable production of NO in the early post-flame region. The HNO mechanism gains importance for rich flames. As the significance of the NNX decreases the share of the HNO attributed to the Prompt might rise and cause the unusual formation beyond the reaction zone. The concentrations and errors are summarized in figure 4.19.

Fig. 4.19: Comparison of Prompt contributions to the total NO formation for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses

4.2.4 Reaction mechanism variation

In this application the kinetic reaction mechanism for the simulations is the GDF. Due to increased divergence caused by the double accounting of minor mechanism. The subtraction analysis is only executed for the main formation pathways. The figure 4.20 summarizes the results of the reaction path analyses. The first plot exhibits the production rates calculated by the SMART in blue and by the subtraction method in light blue. Apart from small deviating fluctuations in the beginning both rates agree very well. For the NNx mechanism the rate from the subtraction method (light orange) fluctuates also in the beginning and reaches a higher peak value than the SMART solution (orange). The decrease, however, coincides for both methods. The third plot demonstrates the calculations for the Prompt production rate. Here the peak values agree very well for the subtraction method (light green) and the SMART (green). Anyhow, deviations in the preheat zone caused by fluctuations in the subtraction solution and a higher prediction for the rate in early post-flame region remain. The last plot demonstrates the contributions to the total NO formation from the distinct chemical routes for both analyses. The scores reveal a good accordance for both methods. Regarding the total NO formation the subtraction calculations yield a relative error of -2.96 % while the relative

Fig. 4.20: Comparison of the NO rate of productions and contributions to the total NO formation for the analysed pathways determined by the distinct reaction path analyses (GDF)

error caused by the SMART is only 0.69 %.

Figure 4.21 compares the total production rates predicted by the SMART algorithm (dashed line) and the subtraction method (dashed-dotted line) with the NO rate of production obtained from the Cantera simulation. For the SMART algorithm the total is the summation of all formation pathways while for the Subtraction method only the main formation pathways are considered, as explained above. The lines show a good alignment. The absolute errors throughout the flame are plotted below. The SMART solutions reveal a comparatively insignificant deviation in the reaction zone. The maximum error has a magnitude of 10^{-5} . The integrated error scores an even smaller value with a magnitude of 10^{-7} . The absolute error calculations of the subtraction method display minor deviations in the beginning and reaches a low point prior to peak production rate caused by the dips in the Thermal and NNX route. In the post-flame zone the predictions for the subtraction method are constantly lower than the NO ROP calculated by Cantera. The maximum error and the integrated error exceed the respective SMART errors by a magnitude of 10^2 .

The solution from the subtraction method applied to the GDF simulation yield

Fig. 4.21: Comparison total NO rates of productions from the reaction path analyses (GDF)

steadier and more relatedable results than the solutions for the GRI simulation. The table 4.4 compares the calculated errors for the total production rate and the total concentration for the GDF and GRI analyses. Regarding the production rate, the errors in the GRI prediction exceed the error in the GDF prediction for the subtraction method by a magnitude of 10^2 . For the total NO formation the relative deviation from the GRI is twice as big as the error made for the GDF mechanism. As for the SMART predictions, the errors for the total production rate have the same magnitude for both applications. The relative error concerning the NO concentration is higher for the GDF mechanism. However, for both applications the error still remains below 1%. A possible explanation for the improved predictions using the GDF are differences in the impacts of the reduced chemistry simulation on the flame structure

Tab. 4.4: Summary of errors in the predictions of the reaction path analyses regarding the use of different kinetic reaction mechanisms

	Total Production rate				Total NO formation	
	Max. abs. error [$\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3\text{s}}$]		Integrated error [$\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3}$]		Relative error [%]	
	<i>Subtraction</i>	<i>SMART</i>	<i>Subtraction</i>	<i>SMART</i>	<i>Subtraction</i>	<i>SMART</i>
GRI	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-7}$	5.92	0.024
GDF	$6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-7}$	2.96	0.69

and temperature. Figure 4.22 shows the relative errors in the temperature between the simulation with a full kinetic mechanism and subset simulation where initiation reaction have been removed. The left plot reveals the errors for the GRI while the right shows the errors for the GDF simulations. For the GRI all subset simulation of the subtraction method cause errors in the temperature curve of the flame. As for the GDF simulations only the removal of the Prompt initiation reaction causes a significant change in the temperature curve around the reaction zone. Towards the end of the flame the Thermal causes decreased temperatures. The greater errors around the reaction zone for the GRI simulations presumably conduce to the unsteady behaviour observed in the Thermal and the NNH production rates and, thus, impair the quality of the outcome.

Fig. 4.22: Relative errors for temperature curves in subset simulations with the GRI mechanism (left) and the GDF mechanism (right)

5 Conclusions

In this thesis, the approach of the SMART algorithm was further improved and examined. The main focus of this work is the evaluation of the algorithm by applying the developed program to a range of premixed methane flames. The results for the extracted NO formation pathways are compared to another RPA method from the literature.

The newly implemented convergence criteria ensure convergence within a reasonable amount of time for all considered applications, while the results show a very good quality of prediction with less than 1 % error to the total NO formation. The main criterion compares the maximum residual to a specified tolerance to monitor and state convergence is reached. The maximum residual is the highest value of the residuals for each pathway through the flame. An additional criterion allows excluding pathways from the residual monitoring when their contribution to the formation of any intermediate species is below a chosen threshold. This way, the simulation time decreases without diminishing the quality of the results. The values for the tolerance and the threshold are supplied via an input so that they are easily adjustable for different applications and purposes. Thus, the decision regarding the compromise between simulation time and accuracy is the user's responsibility.

The study on the convergence performance revealed that the number of required iterations depends on the equivalence ratio and the kinetic mechanism. The behavior of the maximum residuals is similar for lean up to stoichiometric flames, while the residuals of rich flames hit the tolerance after two or three more iterations. However, for all equivalence ratios the total number of iterations is below 10.

Opposed to this, the variation of the kinetic mechanism exhibited a more significant impact on the number of iterations and the simulation time. Here the size of the mechanism strongly correlates with convergence behavior. Small mechanisms with less intermediate species and reactions in the NO_x chemistry sub-model require fewer iterations plus less time for each iteration. The rising complexities of more detailed mechanisms decelerate the process. The most influential factor is the number of intermediate species as the algorithm iterates repeatedly through the species for each flame position. This work examined the simulation times for four reaction mechanisms where the smallest comprises 15 intermediate species and the biggest 37. The simulation time using the smallest mechanism is about one minute while the time required for the convergence

using the biggest mechanism is about 37 minutes. Albeit both convergence times are reasonable, an improved approach regarding the nested loops could save valuable computational time.

For the comparison of reaction path analysis methods, an additional RPA approach was chosen that uses a subtraction technique. The SMART algorithm extracts the main formation pathways (Thermal, Prompt, and NNX) as well as the minor routes (NO_2 , HNO, and Reburn). To match the set of pathways from the SMART, the method from the literature was extended according to the principle idea.

The overall result of the comparison is that the SMART algorithm predicts steady and reasonable production rates for all analyzed NO formation pathways. The calculated total NO rate of productions aligns very well with the respective solution from the flame simulation. This also applies to the total NO formation represented by the concentration of NO at the end of the flame. Here the deviations are less than 1 %. The quality of the results is independent of the equivalence ratio and the kinetic mechanism. The only unexpected behavior of a production rate was uncovered for the Thermal pathway is slightly lean to stoichiometric flames. Here the simplified solution to acknowledge diffusion in the flame has led to a minor elevation of the production rate before the initiation of the formation route. A more sophisticated approach that adjusts the factoring of the diffusion, e.g. by limiting the accounted area in the flame for the calculation of the flux correction factor would presumably diminish the effect. Anyhow, the increase in computational effort might outweigh the benefit of reducing the minor impact of the simplification.

In more detail and concerning the difficulties of the other RPA method, the investigations established the following advantages of the SMART algorithm.

- The SMART algorithm predicts steady and comprehensible results. Apart from the exception mentioned above, the behavior of the production rates matched to the anticipated results. The removal of initiation reactions in the subtraction method causes interference with other pathways leading to unexpected fluctuations and deviations from the expected behavior.
- The SMART algorithm can decouple the minor mechanism from the main formation pathways. The parallel analysis for all pathways and the tracing of fluxes in the SMART algorithm allows separating the minor mechanisms from the main formation pathways. The sequential analysis of the subtraction method returns results for the main formation pathway that include their relative share of production by the minor mechanisms. This is because the minor mechanisms are initiated after nitrogen has been unfixated from N_2 by the principal routes. The additional extraction of the secondary pathways in the subtraction RPA leads to a double accounting in the total NO formation.

- The SMART algorithm predicts steady and reliable results for all analyzed equivalence ratios. Each showed a similar behavior respecting the shape and positioning of the ROPs in flame. The importance of each pathway, respectively the peak rates and the contributions to the overall NO formation increased or decreased according to the specified key characteristics of the examined route for changes in the equivalence ratio. Opposed to this subtraction method failed to extract reliable results for all equivalence ratios. The quality of the results strongly depends on the relative significance of the examined pathway regarding the total NO formation. For routes with small production rates and a comparatively small share in the total formation, interference caused by other more significant mechanisms predominate the results.
- The quality of analysis conducted with the SMART algorithm is independent of the kinetic reaction mechanism. The SMART algorithm predicts for both reaction mechanism results with very small deviations to the total formation rate and NO concentration calculated in the flame simulation. The quality of the solutions from the subtraction method highly depends on the insensitiveness to the partial removal of NO_x chemistry. The higher the errors in the temperature the more significant deviations are found the outcome.
- Considering the execution and interpretation, the SMART algorithm is more convenient. It is a post-processing tool and requires, therefore, no additional simulations of the flame. The results and interim data are easily accessible and ensure a transparent analysis.

In conclusion, the SMART algorithm is an effective and practical tool for reaction path analysis that overcomes the observed hurdles and limitations from other methods. The theory behind the SMART algorithm is universally applicable for reaction pathways so that the algorithm can be adapted for other applications, e.g. for fuel decomposition. Concerning the urgent issue of reducing NO_x and other emissions, the reaction path analysis gains in importance. The SMART algorithm can help to interpret and, thus, to understand the fundamental kinetic mechanisms that are responsible for the pollutant formation.

List of Figures

1.1	NO formation pathways and their approximate significance in dependence on the conditions [23]	2
1.2	Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric propane flame using the element tracing method proposed by Bohon et al. [4] . . .	5
1.3	Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric propane flame using the algorithm developed by Coulmann. [11]	6
2.1	Scheme of prompt-NO in the flame front of a rich CH ₄ -O ₂ -N ₂ flame based on rate of production analysis at the NCN peak location with the GDFkin@3.0 NCN mechanism [29]	14
3.1	Demonstration of a reaction path	18
3.2	Demonstration of total fluxes	18
3.3	Demonstration of accounting fluxes	20
3.4	Flux cases	22
3.5	Flow chart for the pre-processing of the SMART algorithm .	26
3.6	Flow chart for the pre-calculations of the SMART algorithm .	29
3.7	Flow chart for the initialization of the analysis	30
3.8	Flow chart for the analysis of the SMART algorithm	31
3.9	Flow chart for the output of the SMART algorithm	32
3.10	Flow chart of the function for the allocation of fluxes of the SMART algorithm	33
3.11	Residuals for allocation factors, allocated pools and target fluxes over ten iterations for a lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flame (GRI)	36
3.12	NO rate of production of undefined sub-mechanism compared to total rate of production for a lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flame (GRI)	37
3.13	Maximum residuals for premixed methane flames with different equivalence ratios (GRI)	37
3.14	Maximum residuals for lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flames for different kinetic reaction mechanisms	38
3.15	Execution time for lean ($\phi=0.9$) premixed methane flames for different kinetic reaction mechanisms	39

4.1	Relative contributions to the total formation of NO for a pre-mixed methane flame in dependence of the equivalence ratio (GRI-Mech 3.0)	46
4.2	Concentration of selected radicals for a slightly lean ($\phi=0.9$) pre-mixed methane flame (GRI-Mech 3.0)	48
4.3	Reaction path analyses using the subtraction method (top) and the SMART algorithm (bottom) for a slightly lean ($\phi=0.9$) pre-mixed methane flame (GRI-Mech 3.0)	49
4.4	Comparison of the analysed pathways for the subtraction method and the SMART algorithm	50
4.5	Impact of the diffusion simplification on the Thermal route	51
4.6	Interference between the Prompt and the Thermal mechanism caused by the subtraction method	52
4.7	NH concentrations for flame simulations with full and reduced kinetic mechanisms	53
4.8	Comparison of total NO rate of productions from the reaction path analyses	54
4.9	Impact of the minor pathways on the total NO rate of production calculated by the subtraction method	55
4.10	Comparison of contributions from the analysed pathways to the total NO formation	56
4.11	Comparison of the Thermal NO rate of production for a range of equivalence ratios calculated by distinct the reaction path analyses	58
4.12	Comparison of the Thermal peak production for a range of equivalence rates determined by the distinct reaction path analyses	59
4.13	Comparison of Thermal contributions the total NO formation for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses	60
4.14	Comparison of the NNX NO rate of production for a range of equivalence ratios calculated by the distinct reaction path analyses	61
4.15	Comparison of the NNX peak production rates for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses	63
4.16	Comparison of NNX contributions the total NO formation for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses	64
4.17	Comparison of the Prompt NO rate of production for a range of equivalence ratios calculated by the distinct reaction path analyses	65

4.18	Comparison of the Prompt peak production rates for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses	66
4.19	Comparison of Prompt contributions the total NO formation for a range of equivalence ratios determined by the distinct reaction path analyses	67
4.20	Comparison of the NO rate of productions and contributions to the total NO formation for the analysed pathways determined by the distinct reaction path analyses (GDF)	68
4.21	Comparison total NO rates of productions from the reaction path analyses (GDF)	69
4.22	Relative errors for temperature curves in subset simulations with the GRI mechanism (left) and the GDF mechanism (right) .	70

List of Tables

3.1	Intermediate species and reactions for analysed kinetic reaction mechanisms (UCSD, GRI, GDF, Konnov)	38
3.2	Execution time of the pre-analysis (pre-processing and pre-calculations), the analysis and the mean time for one iteration of the analysis.	39
4.1	Summary of reaction path analysis methods	43
4.2	Initiation reactions for the SMART analysis using the GRI-Mech 3.0	45
4.3	Summary of errors for the reaction path analyses	57
4.4	Summary of errors in the predictions of the reaction path analyses regarding the use of different kinetic reaction mechanisms	70

Bibliography

- [1] U. S. Energy Information Administration. *International Energy Outlook 2019*. URL: <https://www.eia.gov/outlooks/ieo/>.
 - [2] P. Dagaut et al. “Experimental and detailed kinetic modeling of nitric oxide re- duction by a natural gas blend in simulated reburning conditions”. In: *Combustion Science and Technology* (1998).
 - [3] D. L. Baulch et al. “Evaluated Kinetic Data for Combustion Modelling”. In: *Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data* 21.3 (1992), pp. 411–734. DOI: 10.1063/1.555908. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.555908>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.555908>.
 - [4] Myles D. Bohon. “Experimental and Kinetic Investigation of the Influence of OH Groups on NOX Formation”. In: X (2016).
 - [5] Myles D. Bohon, Thibault F. Guiberti, S. Mani Sarathy, and William L. Roberts. “Variations in non-thermal NO formation pathways in alcohol flames”. In: *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 36.3 (2017), pp. 3995–4002. ISSN: 15407489. DOI: 10.1016/j.proci.2016.05.024. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2016.05.024>.
 - [6] Myles D. Bohon, Thibault F. Guiberti, and William L. Roberts. “PLIF measurements of non-thermal NO concentrations in alcohol and alkane premixed flames”. In: *Combustion and Flame* 194 (2018), pp. 363–375. ISSN: 15562921. DOI: 10.1016/j.combustflame.2018.05.024. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2018.05.024>.
 - [7] Joseph W Bozzelli and Anthony M Deant. “O + NNH: A Possible New Route”. In: 27 (1995), pp. 1097–1109.
 - [8] Eun Seong Cho and Suk Ho Chung. “Numerical evaluation of NOx mechanisms in methane-air counterflow premixed flames”. In: *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology* 23.3 (2009), pp. 659–666. ISSN: 1738494X. DOI: 10.1007/s12206-008-1222-y.
 - [9] European Comission. *Paris Agreement*. URL: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/international/negotiations/paris_en.
 - [10] Sanjay M. Correa. “A Review of NOx Formation Under Gas-Turbine Combustion Conditions”. In: *Combustion Science and Technology* 87.1-6
-

- (1993), pp. 329–362. DOI: 10.1080/00102209208947221. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00102209208947221>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00102209208947221>.
- [11] Oliver Coulman. “Development and Implementation of a Novel Element Tracing Method for a Reaction Path Analysis and its Application on a NO_x Path Analysis for Deflagration and Detonation Processes”. In: (2019).
- [12] P. Dagaut, J. Luche, and M. Cathonnet. “The kinetics of C1 to C4 hydrocarbons-NO interactions in relation with reburning”. In: *International Symposium on Combustion Abstracts of Accepted Papers* 28.A (2000), pp. 117–118.
- [13] A. El Bakali et al. “NO prediction in natural gas flames using GDF-Kin@3.0 mechanism NCN and HCN contribution to prompt-NO formation”. In: *Fuel* 85.7-8 (2006), pp. 896–909. ISSN: 00162361. DOI: 10.1016/j.fuel.2005.10.012.
- [14] Nancy Faßheber, Marvin C. Schmidt, and Gernot Friedrichs. “Quantitative HNO detection behind shock waves”. In: *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 36.1 (2017), pp. 607–615. ISSN: 15407489. DOI: 10.1016/j.proci.2016.05.035.
- [15] C. P. Fenimore. “Formation of nitric oxide in premixed hydrocarbon flames”. In: *Symposium (International) on Combustion* 13.1 (1971), pp. 373–380. ISSN: 00820784. DOI: 10.1016/S0082-0784(71)80040-1.
- [16] Peter Glarborg, James A. Miller, Branko Ruscic, and Stephen J. Klippenstein. “Modeling nitrogen chemistry in combustion”. In: *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science* 67 (2018), pp. 31–68. ISSN: 03601285. DOI: 10.1016/j.pecs.2018.01.002. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2018.01.002>.
- [17] Hongsheng Guo, Fengshan Liu, and Gregory J. Smallwood. “A numerical study on NO_x formation in laminar counterflow CH₄/air triple flames”. In: *Combustion and Flame* 143.3 (2005), pp. 282–298. ISSN: 00102180. DOI: 10.1016/j.combustflame.2005.06.004.
- [18] Hongsheng Guo and Gregory J. Smallwood. “A numerical investigation on NO_x formation in counterflow n-heptane triple flames”. In: *International Journal of Thermal Sciences* 46.9 (2007), pp. 936–943. ISSN: 12900729. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijthermalsci.2006.11.002.
- [19] Hongsheng Guo et al. “The effect of hydrogen addition on flammability limit and NO_x emission in ultra-lean counterflow CH₄/air premixed

- flames". In: *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 30.1 (2005), pp. 303–311. ISSN: 15407489. DOI: 10.1016/j.proci.2004.08.177.
- [20] Stine Hansen and Peter Glarborg. "Simplified model for reburning chemistry". In: *Energy and Fuels* 24.8 (2010), pp. 4185–4192. ISSN: 08870624. DOI: 10.1021/ef100469h.
- [21] S.C. Hill and L. Douglas Smoot. "Modeling of nitrogen oxides formation and destruction in combustion systems." In: *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* (2000).
- [22] K.H. Homann. *Reaktionskinetik*. Steinkopff-Verlag Heidelberg, 1975. ISBN: 978-3-642-72314-8. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-72314-8.
- [23] F. Joos. *Technische Verbrennung; Verbrennungstechnik, Verbrennungsmodellierung, Emissionen*. Springer, 2006. ISBN: 9783540343332. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330670823.
- [24] Yiguang Ju and Takashi Niioka. "Computation of NO_x emission of a methane - air diffusion flame in a two-dimensional laminar jet with detailed chemistry". In: *Combustion Theory and Modelling* 1.3 (1997), pp. 243–258. ISSN: 17413559. DOI: 10.1080/715695654.
- [25] Stephen J. Klippenstein, Lawrence B. Harding, Peter Glarborg, and James A. Miller. "The role of NNH in NO formation and control". In: *Combustion and Flame* 158.4 (2011), pp. 774–789. ISSN: 00102180. DOI: 10.1016/j.combustflame.2010.12.013. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2010.12.013>.
- [26] A. A. Konnov. "Implementation of the NCN pathway of prompt-NO formation in the detailed reaction mechanism". In: *Combustion and Flame* 156.11 (2009), pp. 2093–2105. ISSN: 00102180. DOI: 10.1016/j.combustflame.2009.03.016. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2009.03.016>.
- [27] A. A. Konnov, G. Colson, and J. De Ruyck. "The new route forming NO via NNH". In: *Combustion and Flame* 121.3 (2000), pp. 548–550. ISSN: 00102180. DOI: 10.1016/S0010-2180(99)00164-9.
- [28] Alexander A. Konnov, Igor V. Dyakov, and Jacques De Ruyck. "Nitric oxide formation in premixed flames of H₂ + CO + CO₂ and air". In: *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 29.2 (2002), pp. 2171–2177. ISSN: 15407489. DOI: 10.1016/S1540-7489(02)80264-4.
- [29] N. Lamoureux, A. Desgroux, A. El Bakali, and J.F. Pauwels. "Experimental and numerical study of the role of NCN in prompt-NO formation

- in low-pressure CH₄-O₂-N₂ and C₂H₂-O₂-N₂ flames”. In: *Combustion and Flame* (2010).
- [30] P. C. Malte and D. T. Pratt. “Measurement of atomic oxygen and nitrogen oxides in jet-stirred combustion”. In: *Symposium (International) on Combustion* 15.1 (1975), pp. 1061–1070. ISSN: 00820784. DOI: 10.1016/S0082-0784(75)80371-7.
- [31] James A. Miller and Craig T. Bowman. “Mechanism and Modeling of Nitrogen Chemistry in Combustion”. In: *Prog. Energy Combustion* 15 (1989), pp. 287–338.
- [32] L.V. Moskaleva and M.C. Lin. “The spin-conserved reaction CH+N₂→H+NCN: A major pathway to prompt NO studied by quantum/statistical theory calculations and kinetic modeling of rate constant”. In: *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* (2000).
- [33] A. L. Myerson. “The Reduction of Nitric Oxide in Simulated Combustion Effluents by Hydrocarbon-Oxygen Mixtures.” In: *Fifteenth Symposium (International’s 011 Combustion*. (1974), p. 1085.
- [34] Sameer V. Naik and Normand M. Laurendeau. “Lif measurements and chemical kinetic analysis of nitric oxide formation in high-pressure counterflow partially premixed and nonpremixed flames”. In: *Combustion Science and Technology* 176.11 (2004), pp. 1809–1853. ISSN: 00102202. DOI: 10.1080/00102200490504472.
- [35] I. Nassi and B. Shneiderman. “Flowchart Techniques for Structured Programming”. In: *SIGPLAN Not.* 8.8 (Aug. 1973), 12–26. ISSN: 0362-1340. DOI: 10.1145/953349.953350. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/953349.953350>.
- [36] M. Nishioka, S. Nakagawa, Y. Ishikawa, and T. Takeno. “NO emission characteristics of methane-air double flame”. In: *Combustion and Flame* 98.1-2 (1994), pp. 127–138. ISSN: 00102180. DOI: 10.1016/0010-2180(94)90203-8.
- [37] Sangwoon Park and Yongmo Kim. “Effects of nitrogen dilution on the NO_x formation characteristics of CH₄/CO/H₂ syngas counterflow non-premixed flames”. In: *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 42.16 (2017), pp. 11945–11961. ISSN: 03603199. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.02.080. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.02.080>.
- [38] L. Prada and J. A. Miller. “Reburning using several hydrocarbon fuels: A kinetic modeling study”. In: *Combustion Science and Tech-*

- nology* 132.1-6 (1998), pp. 225–250. ISSN: 00102202. DOI: 10.1080/00102209808952016.
- [39] Mechanical University of California at San Diego and Aerospace Engineering (Combustion Research). *Chemical-kinetic mechanisms for combustion applications*. 2018. URL: <http://combustion.ucsd.edu>.
- [40] Taeko Sano. “NO₂ Formation in Laminar Flames”. In: *Combustion Science and Technology* 29.3-6 (1982), pp. 261–275. ISSN: 1563521X. DOI: 10.1080/00102208208923601.
- [41] G.P. Smith et al. *GRI-Mech 3.0*. 1999. URL: http://www.me.berkeley.edu/gri_mech/.
- [42] Dieter Stapf and Wolfgang Leuckel. “Flow reactor studies and testing of comprehensive mechanisms for NO_x reburning”. In: *Symposium (International) on Combustion* 26.2 (1996), pp. 2083–2090. ISSN: 00820784. DOI: 10.1016/S0082-0784(96)80032-4.
- [43] Hai Wang. “Combustion Chemistry”. In: (2012).
- [44] J. Warnatz, U. Maas, and R. W. Dibble. *Combustion*. 4th. c. Springer, 2006, pp. 2–6. ISBN: 9783540259923.
- [45] Graeme M.G. Watson, Jeffrey D. Munzar, and Jeffrey M. Bergthorson. “NO formation in model syngas and biogas blends”. In: *Fuel* 124.x (2014), pp. 113–124. ISSN: 00162361. DOI: 10.1016/j.fuel.2014.01.079. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2014.01.079>.
- [46] Y. B. Zeldovich. “The oxidation of nitrogen in combustion and explosions”. In: *Acta Physicochim U.R.S.S.* 21 (1946), pp. 577–628.
- [47] Yingjia Zhang et al. “Assesing the predictions of a NO_x kinetic mechanism”. In: *Combustion and Flame* 182 (2017), pp. 122–141. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2017.03.019>.

Appendix A

Initiation reactions for the SMART analysis using the GDF-Kin 3.0 NCN

Sub-mechanism	Reaction equation	Reaction #
Thermal	$N_2 + O \rightarrow NO + N$	R699
NNX	$NNH + M \leftarrow N_2 + H + M$	R738
	$N_2O (+M) \leftarrow N_2 + O (+M)$	R778
Prompt	$CN + N \leftarrow C + N_2$	R826
	$CH_2 + N_2 \rightarrow HCN + NH$	R867
	$CH + N_2 \rightarrow H + NCN$	R868
NO2	$HO_2 + NO \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + OH$	R762
	$H + NO_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + OH$	R767
	$NO_2 + O \rightleftharpoons NO + O_2$	R768
	$NO + O + M \rightleftharpoons NO_2 + M$	R769
HNO	$H + NO + M \rightleftharpoons HNO + M$	R212
	$HNO + O \rightleftharpoons NO + OH$	R745
	$HNO + OH \rightleftharpoons H_2O + NO$	R746
	$H + HNO \rightleftharpoons H_2 + NO$	R747
	$HNO + O_2 \rightleftharpoons HO_2 + NO$	R751
	$H + NO + M \rightleftharpoons HNO + M$	R764
Reburn	$HCO + NO \rightarrow CO + HNO$	R765
	$C + NO \rightarrow CN + O$	R783
	$CH + NO \rightarrow HCN + O$	R784
	$NO + SCH_2 \rightarrow HCN + OH$	R785
	$CH_2 + NO \rightarrow H + HCNO$	R786
	$CH_2 + NO \rightarrow HCN + OH$	R787
	$CH_3 + NO \rightarrow H_2O + HCN$	R788
	$CH_3 + NO \rightarrow H_2CN + OH$	R789
	$HCCO + NO \rightarrow CO + HCNO$	R790
	$HCCO + NO \rightarrow CO_2 + HCN$	R791
	$HCNO + O \leftarrow HCO + NO$	R793
	$HCNO + OH \leftarrow CH_2O + NO$	R794
	$CN + NO \rightarrow N + NCO$	R819
	$CN + NO \rightarrow CO + N_2$	R820
	$CN + HNO \leftarrow HCN + NO$	R821
	$CN + NO_2 \leftarrow NCO + NO$	R828
	$CN + N_2O \leftarrow NCN + NO$	R829
	$NCO + NO \rightarrow CO_2 + N_2$	R839
	$HNO + NCO \leftarrow HNCO + NO$	R842
	$NCO + OH \leftarrow HCO + NO$	R848
	$NCN + O \leftarrow CN + NO$	R854
	$NCN + OH \leftarrow HCN + NO$	R855
	$NCN + O_2 \leftarrow NCO + NO$	R856
	$CO_2 + N \leftarrow CH_2O + NO$	R878
	$CH_3O + HNO \leftarrow CH_3OH + NO$	R882

Appendix B

```
Variables:
  flame_sim
      { string -var., directory of flame simulation file }

  flpos   { int -var., counter for flame positions }

  flpos_it_max
      { int -var., maximum number of iterations for the
        while-loop (termination criterion) }

  flpos_residual
      { int -var., residual for the allocated fluxes of current
        the flame position }

  flpos_tol
      { int -var., tolerance of the convergence criterion for
        current the flame position }

  i       { int -var., counter for iteration }

  initiation_reactant
      { string -var., initiation species (→ inputs_dict ) }

  n_submech
      { int -var., number of sub-mechanisms (→ inputs_dict
        ) }
```

Variables:

```
    reac_mech      { string -var., directory of reaction mechanism file }

    rpa_residual   { real -var., max. residual in allocation factors,
                   allocated pools and target fluxes }

    rpa_it         { int -var., counter for RPA iterations }

    rpa_tol        { real -var., tolerance for RPA (→ inputs_dict ) }

    setup          { string -var., directory of setup file }

    start          { int -var., start position for iteration through flame }

    step           { int -var., stepsize for iteration through flame }

    stop           { int -var., end position for iteration through flame }

    sub_it_max     { int -var., maximum number of iterations for the
                   while-loop (termination criterion) }

    sub_mechs      { string -var., directory of sub-mechanism input file }

    sub_residual   { real -var., residual for the allocated fluxes of the
                   current sub-mechanism and at the flame position }

    sub_tol        { real -var., tolerance of the convergence criterion for
                   the current sub-mechanism and the flame position }

    target_species { string -var., target species (→ inputs_dict ) }

    threshold      { real -var., threshold for convergence criteria (→
                   inputs_dict ) }

    tracking_element { string -var., tracking element (→ inputs_dict ) }
```

Arrays:

allocated_fluxes
 { real -4D-array, allocated fluxes between each pair of species [1.D,2.D], for each sub-mechanism plus the sum [3.D], and for each flame position [4.D] [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]}
 allocated_fluxes_flpos
 { real -3D-array, allocated fluxes between each pair of species [1.D,2.D], for each sub-mechanism plus the sum [3.D] at the analysed flame position [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]}
 allocated_fluxes_sub_0
 { real -4D-array, allocated fluxes sub-mechanism between each pair of species [1.D,2.D], for each sub-mechanism plus the sum [3.D], and for each flame position [4.D] [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]} (previous iteration)
 allocated_pools
 { real -3D-array, allocated pools for each species (1.D), for each sub-mechanism (2.D), and for each flame position (3.D) [$\frac{kmol}{m^3}$]}
 allocated_pools_flpos
 { real -2D-array, allocated pools for each species [1.D], for each sub-mechanism[2.D] at analysed flame position [$\frac{kmol}{m^3}$]}
 allocation_factors
 { real -3D-array, allocation factors for each species (1.D)], for each sub-mechanism (2.D), and for each flame position (3.D)}
 allocation_factors_flpos
 { real -2D-array, allocation factors for each species [1.D], for each sub-mechanism [2.D] at the analysed flame position}
 allocation_factors_updated
 { real -3D-array, allocation factors for each species [1.D], for each sub-mechanism [2.D], and for each flame position [3.D] updated by recent iteration}

Arrays:

fcf	{ real -2D-array, flux correction factors for each species [1.D] and for each sub-mechanism [2.D]}
global_fluxes	{ real -3D-array, global fluxes between each pair of species [1.D,2.D] and for each flame position [3.D] [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]} [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]
global_fluxes_flpos	{ real -2D-array, global fluxes between each pair of species [1.D,2.D] at the analysed flame position [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]} [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]
initiation_fluxes	{ real -4D-array, initiation fluxes between each pair of species [1.D,2.D], for each sub-mechanism [3.D], and for each flame position [4.D] [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]} [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]
p	{ real -1D-array, pressure in flame simulation [Pa] (\rightarrow flame_dict)}
pools	{ real -2D-array, pools for each species (1.D) and for each flame position (2.D) [$\frac{kmol}{m^3}$]} [$\frac{kmol}{m^3}$]
pool_contributions_flpos	{ real -2D-array, contributions to the pools for each species (1.D) for the analysed flame position (2.D) [$\frac{kmol}{m^3}$]} [$\frac{kmol}{m^3}$]
t	{ real -1D-array, time vector in flame simulation [s] (\rightarrow flame_dict)}
T	{ real -1D-array, temperatur in flame simulation [K] (\rightarrow flame_dict)}
target_fluxes	{ real -2D-array, net fluxes of target species for each sub-mechanism (1.D) and for each flame position (2.D)} [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$] [$\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$]

Arrays:

```

target_fluxes_updated
    { real -2D-array, net fluxes of target species for each
      sub-mechanism (1.D) and for each flame position
      (2.D) updated by recent iteration [ $\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$ ]}

total_flux_net
    { real -2D-array, Total net fluxes for each species
      (1.D) and for each flame position (2.D) [ $\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$ ]}

total_flux_net_fpos
    { real -1D-array, Total net fluxes for each species at
      the analysed flame position [ $\frac{kmol}{m^3s}$ ]}

x
    { real -1D-array, position vector in flame simulation
      [m] ( $\rightarrow$  flame_dict )}

```

Lists:

```

initiation_reactions
    { int -list, nested list of initiation reactions sorted
      by direction and sub-mechanism (  $\rightarrow$  inputs_dict )}

int_species
    { string -list, list of intermediate species (  $\rightarrow$ 
      inputs_dict )}

reactions_between_species
    { int -list, nested lists of association numbers of
      reactions between the intermediate species.}

sub_mech_names
    { string -list, list of sub-mechanisms' names (  $\rightarrow$ 
      inputs_dict )}

```

Dictionaries:

```

flame_dict
    { Dictionary , Dictionary for the flame simulation file
      data}

inputs_dict
    { Dictionary , Dictionary for all inputs}

outputs_dict
    { Dictionary , Dictionary for all outputs}

```